

Blast waves in magnetized plasmas

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Abstract

Dimensional analysis allowed the discovery of a physical law governing the propagation of a spherical blast wave generated by a punctual and instantaneous energy deposit in a gas. This law, generally known as the Taylor-von Neumann-Sedov solution, has been applied in astrophysics to model supernova blast waves in interstellar plasmas. However, some astronomical observations have shown the existence of non-spherical supernova blast waves. It is suspected that this anisotropy is partly due to the presence of an ambient magnetic field, but the description of a blast wave in such a context remains incomplete. The aim of this study is to model the propagation of a blast wave in a magnetized plasma. The main tools used are dimensional analysis, the ab initio method, based on the equations of magnetohydrodynamics, and numerical simulation. This study results in an analytical model describing the propagation of a blast wave in a magnetized plasma, and its transformation into a magnetic shock. In addition, scaling laws are proposed for the study of supernova blast waves through laboratory experiments consisting of laser shots.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

1.1.1 Blast waves

A shock wave is a violent propagating disturbance that moves faster than the local speed of sound in the medium. A blast wave is a shock wave produced by an explosion. It can be modelled as an expanding surface of pressure discontinuity, resulting from the instantaneous deposition of a large amount of energy in a small, very localised volume. It is followed by a blast wind of negative gauge pressure, which sucks items back in towards the center of the explosion.

The propagation of a blast wave in an ideal gas has been studied independently by Geoffrey Ingram Taylor [1], John von Neumann [2] and Leonid Sedov [3] during World War II. The original works of these authors having been classified, they were completed and released some years later in other publications [4, 5, 6].

1.1.2 Laser shots

Experiments can be conducted in the laboratory to simulate intense explosions and the resulting blast waves. These are usually laser shots, which increase the temperature of small targets in a very short time, allowing a significant, fast and localized energy deposit. The propagation of the blast wave is then observed in the firing chamber using various measuring instruments.

1.1.3 Supernovae

A supernova is the set of phenomena that result from the implosion of a star at the end of its life, notably a gigantic explosion that is accompanied by a brief but huge increase in its luminosity. A supernova remnant (SNR) is the structure resulting from the explosion of a star in a supernova. It consists of ejected material expanding from the explosion center and it is bounded by the expanding blast wave.

(a) Picture named "Hubble Supernova Bubble Resembles Holiday Ornament" from NASA, ESA and the Hubble Heritage Team (2010 December 14).

(b) Picture named "M1: The Incredible Expanding Crab" from Adam Block, Mt. Lemmon SkyCenter, U. Arizona (2013 September 5).

Figure 1: Observations of supernovae.

In figure 1a the pristine shell, or bubble, is the result of gas that is being shocked by the expanding blast wave from a supernova. The bubble-shaped shroud of gas is 23 light-years across and is expanding at more than

5 000 kilometers per second. The Crab Nebula, shown in figure 1b, is now known to be a SNR. The violent birth of the Crab was witnessed by Chinese astronomers in the year 1054. Roughly 10 light-years across today, the nebula is still expanding at a rate of over 1 000 kilometers per second. Its non-spherical shape makes it a striking example of anisotropic and filamentary blast wave.

1.1.4 Magnetohydrodynamics

Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) is a scientific discipline that describes the behavior of an electrically conducting fluid in the presence of electromagnetic fields. It applies in particular to plasmas. In the field of astrophysics, where the electrical conductivity is assumed to be infinite, the ideal MHD is commonly used. In ideal MHD, a fluid is completely described by its velocity, mass density, pressure, heat capacity ratio and magnetic field.

1.2 Problem

As soon as a magnetic field is added, the physical phenomena occurring in an MHD system generally become difficult to predict. In this case, a blast wave resulting from an intense explosion will be modified by the addition of a magnetic field in a way that is not yet well understood. This study aims to develop tools to describe the expansion of a blast wave in a plasma experiencing an ambient magnetic field. This can be done, among other things, through scaling laws. The latter allow, for example, the prediction of interstellar phenomena from experiments conducted in laboratories, and more particularly, from laser shots. Another aspect of the study will concern the search for an analytical solution to the problem.

The *Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives* (CEA) provides a program for the numerical simulation of MHD systems called conservation laws of various ionized systems (CLOVIS). This program will be used to simulate explosions in magnetized or non-magnetized plasmas. Another program called post-processing for blast wave simulations (POSTBLAST) is developed during this study for processing the simulation results of CLOVIS. It is used for extracting simulation output data, calculating additional quantities, and generating the figures shown in this document.

1.2.1 Physical quantities involved

The main physical constants and generic quantities involved in the problem are: k_B the Boltzmann constant (J/K), μ_0 the vacuum permeability (H/m), ε_0 the vacuum permittivity (F/m), B the magnetic field (T), ρ the mass density (kg/m³), n the number density (m⁻³), P the pressure (Pa), T the temperature (K), v the speed (m/s), r the radius (m), V the volume (m³), U the internal energy (J) and t the time (s). The units of the physical quantities are expressed with the base or derived units of the *système international d'unités* (SI).

More precisely, the following quantities will be used to characterize the physical system before the stellar explosion: B_0 is the norm of the ambient constant magnetic field, ρ_0 is the mass density of the plasma, n_0 is the number density of the plasma, P_0 is the pressure of the plasma, T_0 is the temperature of the plasma and v_0 is the velocity of the plasma. The moment of the explosion is noted t_0 . It is arbitrarily written $t_0 = 0$. In the following, it is assumed that the permittivity and permeability of the plasma are the vacuum permeability μ_0 and the vacuum permittivity ε_0 .

The explosive core is characterized with the following quantities: r_c is the radius delimiting the region of space in which the energy is deposited, V_c is the volume of the region of space in which the energy is deposited and U_d is the energy of the supernova deposited at $t = t_0$. Finally, $r(t)$ gives the position of the blast wave front from the explosion center. At the time t_0 of the explosion $r = r_c$. The region of space in which the energy is deposited is usually considered to be punctual, but r_c and V_c are still defined here even if they tend to 0 later on.

1.2.2 Geometries

In order to observe how the physical laws generalize, the problem is declined and studied in three idealized geometries presented below. What distinguishes the three cases is the shape of the region in which the energy is deposited. Regardless of the shape, the space outside the region where the energy is deposited is occupied by a completely ionized, homogeneous plasma, characterized by the variables μ_0 , ε_0 , ρ_0 , n_0 , P_0 , T_0 and v_0 . The undisturbed plasma is supposed to be static, and therefore $v_0 = 0$ in the reference frame of the star. In all

Figure 2: Blast wave in point source geometry.

geometries, an ambient magnetic field \vec{B}_0 of component B_0 along \vec{u}_z is added. A quantity a , similar from one geometry to another, can be denoted respectively a , a' , and a'' in the three geometries presented below. To refer to a quantity, without specifying in which geometry, the notation a^* can be used.

The most consistent geometry with a spherical supernova explosion is shown in figure 2. In the latter, the center of gravity of the star is located at the origin of the reference frame $(O, \vec{u}_x, \vec{u}_y, \vec{u}_z)$. The energy U_d is deposited in a ball centered in O , of radius r_c , and volume $V_c = (4/3)\pi r_c^3$. The spherical coordinate system (r, θ, φ) is privileged here. In the following, this geometry is called the *point source geometry*.

The second geometry is shown in figure 3. In this geometry, the energy U_d is deposited in a cylinder of axis \vec{u}_z , height L_c , radius r_c , and volume $V_c = L_c \pi r_c^2$. It is assumed that $L_c \rightarrow +\infty$. This justifies the usual infinite cylinder assumption. With a non-zero volume density of energy, the consequence is that $U_d \rightarrow +\infty$. This is why the energy per unit length U_d/L_c is used as a parameter for this geometry, rather than U_d . The cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ, z) is privileged. In the following, this geometry is called the *line source geometry*.

The third and last geometry is shown in figure 4. Here, the energy U_d is deposited in a cuboid whose edges parallel to the axes $\vec{u}_x, \vec{u}_y, \vec{u}_z$ are respectively of length r_c, L_c, L_c , and whose volume is $V_c = 2r_c L_c^2$. It is also assumed that $L_c \rightarrow +\infty$. Again, this is why the energy per unit area U_d/L_c^2 is used as a parameter for this geometry, rather than U_d . In the following, this geometry is called the *plane source geometry*.

1.2.3 Symmetries and invariances

In the point source geometry, the initial physical quantities are invariant with respect to φ . Moreover, all quantities, except the magnetic field \vec{B}_0 , are also invariant with respect to θ . Thus, without an ambient magnetic field, the system has a spherical symmetry, and the blast wave takes the shape of an expanding sphere. When the magnetic field is taken into account, the geometry of the system becomes circular, and the blast wave takes a shape that can be described by a surface of revolution around \vec{u}_z . At $t = t_0$, the system is in a state that meets the conditions of existence of a plane of symmetry Π_S , as stated in appendix B.3. The latter symmetry plane is perpendicular to \vec{u}_z , passes through the center of the star, and remains valid for $t > t_0$. At any point in the plane Π_S , the resulting magnetic field \vec{B} remains perpendicular to Π_S .

In the line source geometry, the initial physical quantities are invariant with respect to φ . Using the infinite cylinder assumption, they are also invariant with respect to z . Thus, in this geometry, the blast wave takes the shape of an expanding cylinder. The conditions from appendix B.3 are met to justify that any plane normal to \vec{u}_z is a plane of symmetry Π_S . Since each cut of the cylinder is the same, it is possible to reduce this geometry to a two-dimensional (2D) problem in Π_S . At any time, the resulting magnetic field \vec{B} is perpendicular to Π_S .

In the plane source geometry, the initial physical quantities are invariant with respect to y and z . Here, the blast wave is assimilated to two planes normal to \vec{u}_x , moving away from each other. Again, the conditions

Figure 3: Blast wave in line source geometry.

from appendix B.3 are met to justify that any plane normal to \vec{u}_z is a plane of symmetry Π_S . It is possible to reduce this geometry to a one-dimensional (1D) problem along \vec{u}_x . The resulting magnetic field \vec{B} remains perpendicular to Π_S .

1.2.4 Ideal plasma

In the interstellar medium (ISM), and more specifically in warm ionized medium (WIM) and hot ionized medium (HIM), the particle densities are small and the temperatures are huge [7]. In these areas, where stars are born and die, the coupling parameter Γ is therefore very small compared to unity. As discussed in appendix A.4, it is then justified to apply the ideal plasma assumption. This means that the potential energy due to interparticle electrostatic forces is less significant compared with the kinetic energy. Each particle has an average kinetic energy equal to $(d_f/2)k_B T$, where d_f is the number of degrees of freedom of a particle. The plasma is then modelled as an ideal gas, and its equation of state is written:

$$P = nk_B T \quad (1)$$

With the ideal plasma assumption, the internal energy U of the plasma is the sum of the kinetic energies of its particles. Its expression, and other equations related to ideal gases, are given in appendix A.2.2. At $t = t_0$, the instantaneous deposit of energy U_d leads to a large temperature and pressure increase in the explosive core. It is assumed here that the pressure P_c in the explosive core, resulting from the deposit of energy U_d at $t = t_0$, is very large in comparison of the pressure P_0 of the initial plasma. With $\gamma = (d_f + 2)/d_f$ the adiabatic index of the ideal plasma, the pressure in the explosive core at $t = t_0$ is given by:

$$P_c \approx (\gamma - 1) \frac{U_d}{V_c} \gg P_0 \quad (2)$$

The only possible motion of a particle in a monoatomic gas is translation (in the three spatial directions). Therefore $d_f = 3$ for a monoatomic gas. For a diatomic gas, two additional axes of rotation must be taken into account, which gives $d_f = 5$. As the blast wave propagates, the pressure jump decreases. In the absence of a magnetic field, and after a sufficiently long time, the energy released by the explosion is almost completely

Figure 4: Blast wave in plane source geometry.

dissipated, and the blast wave turns into a sound wave. The speed of sound v_s in the initial plasma can be expressed easily thanks to the ideal plasma assumption:

$$v_s = \sqrt{\gamma \frac{P_0}{\rho_0}} \quad (3)$$

The front of the blast wave, or in other words, the surface marking the abrupt change in pressure, temperature and density of the medium, moves at supersonic speed. A blast wave is therefore characterized by a very large Mach number M . The latter is expressed as the ratio of the speed dr/dt of the blast wave front to the speed of sound v_s in the medium:

$$M = \frac{1}{v_s} \frac{dr}{dt} \quad (4)$$

The speed of sound being isotropic, the shape of the blast wave in the absence of a magnetic field will remain a priori unchanged while it turns into a sound wave.

1.2.5 Effects of the magnetic field

Any magnetic field \vec{B} has an associated magnetic pressure P_B . It is identical to any other physical pressure except that it is carried by the magnetic field rather than by the microscopic agitation of gas particles. A gradient in field strength causes a force due to the magnetic pressure gradient called the magnetic pressure force. The magnetic pressure is written:

$$P_B = \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} \quad (5)$$

The problem can be considered with and without an ambient magnetic field \vec{B}_0 . However, when the latter is taken into account, it is assumed that its resulting magnetic pressure is much lower than the pressure P_c in the explosive core. As for equation (2), it is sufficient in practice to make the volume V_c small enough so that the pressure P_c is arbitrarily large:

$$P_c \gg P_{B_0} \quad (6)$$

Another quantity to characterize the undisturbed plasma is the Alfvén speed v_A . The latter is related to the speed of Alfvén waves and magnetosonic waves, detailed in annex A.5.5. In the same way that a disturbance in hydrodynamics results in a sound wave, a disturbance in MHD will result in a magnetosonic wave. Thus, it is already expected that the blast wave will progressively transform into a magnetosonic wave when an ambient magnetic field is taken into account. The Alfvén speed in the initial plasma is given by:

$$v_A = \sqrt{2 \frac{P_{B_0}}{\rho_0}} \quad (7)$$

Comparing equations (3) and (7), it may be tempting to define a magnetic analogue of γ , which would take the value $\gamma_B = 2$ and would play a role similar to the heat capacity ratio for P_B . By extension, this would give a virtual number of degrees of freedom $d_f = 2$. Finally, there is also a magnetic equivalent of the Mach number called the Alfvén number. It turns out that the Alfvén number A will take an importance similar to that of the Mach number in the following. It is defined as the ratio of the speed dr/dt of the blast wave front to the Alfvén speed v_A in the medium:

$$A = \frac{1}{v_A} \frac{dr}{dt} \quad (8)$$

As shown by the figure 29 in section A.5.5 the magnetosonic speeds are anisotropic. The blast wave is therefore likely to be deformed as it transforms into a magnetosonic wave.

2 Analytical methods

2.1 Dimensionless numbers

2.1.1 Dimensional analysis method

Like many phenomena in hydrodynamics (HD) and MHD, the theory does not directly allow the expression of an analytical solution to the problem studied here. In this case, it is common to proceed with dimensional analysis in order to form dimensionless numbers from the quantities that are considered relevant in the description of the problem. For this, the first step is to identify all the physical quantities x_i that characterize the physical system, whether they are constants, functions or variables.

The quantities encountered so far, and *a priori* sufficient to describe the system, are: γ , v_0 , ρ_0 , P_0 , B_0 , μ_0 , r , r_c , t and U_d (in the point source geometry), U_d/L_c (in the line source geometry) or U_d/L_c^2 (in the plane source geometry). The initial speed v_0 can be left aside since the pre-existing plasma is at rest. Moreover, since the explosive core is considered punctual, the core radius r_c is also left out. Finally, in each geometry, a number $\mathcal{N} = 8$ of relevant physical quantities x_i can be retained.

The second step is to write the dimension matrix. The physical quantities x_i of the problem are expressed in table 1 through the basic physical dimensions: T the time, L the length, M the mass, I the electric current, Θ the thermodynamic temperature, N the amount of substance and J the luminous intensity. Since Θ , N, and J are not contained in the dimensions of the selected physical quantities, they are removed from table 1. The third step is to calculate the rank \mathcal{R} of the dimension matrix. Here, \mathcal{R} is equal to 4.

The fourth step is to choose \mathcal{R} base quantities b_j . These quantities must be constant and dimensionally independent. The base quantities can be chosen among the x_i if they are constant. Otherwise, if x_i is a function or a variable, it is possible to take the initial or boundary condition. It can be judicious sometimes to form base quantities from products or quotients of the x_i . Here, the \mathcal{R} base quantities chosen are: ρ_0 , P_0 , μ_0 , and U_d (in the point source geometry), U_d/L_c (in the line source geometry) or U_d/L_c^2 (in the plane source geometry). The fifth step is to form the \mathcal{N} characteristic scales X_i such that $[X_i] = [x_i]$ by combining the \mathcal{R} base quantities b_j . Finally, the dimensionless numbers are given by $N_i = (x_i/X_i)^{a_i}$ with a_i an arbitrary exponent.

i	x_i	T	L	M	I
1*	γ	0	0	0	0
2*	ρ_0	0	-3	1	0
3*	P_0	-2	-1	1	0
4*	B_0	-2	0	1	-1
5*	μ_0	-2	1	1	-2
6*	r	0	1	0	0
7*	t	1	0	0	0
8	U_d	-2	2	1	0
8'	U_d/L_c	-2	1	1	0
8''	U_d/L_c^2	-2	0	1	0

Table 1: Dimension matrix of the physical quantities.

i	x_i	X_i	N_i
1	γ	1	γ
4	B_0	$P_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \mu_0^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$\frac{B_0^2}{\mu_0 P_0}$
6	r	$P_0^{-\frac{1}{3}} U_d^{\frac{1}{3}}$	$\frac{r^3 P_0}{U_d}$
7	t	$\rho_0^{\frac{1}{2}} P_0^{-\frac{5}{6}} U_d^{\frac{1}{3}}$	$\frac{t^6 P_0^5}{\rho_0^3 U_d^2}$

Table 2: Characteristic scales and dimensionless numbers in the point source geometry.

i	x_i	X_i	N_i
1'	γ	1	γ
4'	B_0	$P_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \mu_0^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$\frac{B_0^2}{\mu_0 P_0}$
6'	r	$P_0^{-\frac{1}{2}} (U_d/L_c)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$\frac{r^2 P_0 L_c}{U_d}$
7'	t	$\rho_0^{\frac{1}{2}} P_0^{-1} (U_d/L_c)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$\frac{t^4 P_0^4 L_c^2}{\rho_0^2 U_d^2}$

Table 3: Characteristic scales and dimensionless numbers in the line source geometry.

i	x_i	X_i	N_i
1''	γ	1	γ
4''	B_0	$P_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \mu_0^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$\frac{B_0^2}{\mu_0 P_0}$
6''	r	$P_0^{-1} (U_d/L_c^2)$	$\frac{r P_0 L_c^2}{U_d}$
7''	t	$\rho_0^{\frac{1}{2}} P_0^{-\frac{3}{2}} (U_d/L_c^2)$	$\frac{t^2 P_0^3 L_c^4}{\rho_0 U_d^2}$

Table 4: Characteristic scales and dimensionless numbers in the plane source geometry.

As shown in tables 2, 3 and 4, dimensional analysis method, applied to the selected quantities, results in four dimensionless numbers in each geometry. If the physical quantities are indeed sufficient to describe the problem, the Buckingham π theorem then states the existence, in each geometry, of a function f^* governing the system and such that $f^*(N_1^*, N_4^*, N_6^*, N_7^*) = 0$. The question now is how useful this result is.

When only one dimensionless number results from the dimensional analysis, it is easy to propose a physical law by setting this number equal to a constant. However, in the present case, it might be very difficult to determine an empirical expression of f^* , given the number of parameters. Second, there is no guarantee that all relevant physical quantities, and only those, have been chosen. Indeed the choice remains arbitrary and a more rigorous and systematic method of quantity selection would be welcome.

2.1.2 Equation invariance method

Another way to form dimensionless numbers is to start from the equations of the model. Here, the model used for the description of the problem is the ideal MHD. Its equations are given in section A.5.3. The principle of the method is as follows. Let Σ and $\bar{\Sigma}$ be two physical systems at different scales. In Σ , the physical quantities are noted x , whereas in $\bar{\Sigma}$ they are noted \bar{x} . The quantities x and \bar{x} are related by the relation $\bar{x} = k_x x$ with k_x a coefficient that reflects the change of scale between Σ and $\bar{\Sigma}$. Imposing the invariance of the equations of the model corresponds to asking that the equations written with the variables \bar{x} are strictly identical to the equations written with the variables x . To simplify the calculations, k_x is replaced by b^{a_x} with b a base common to all x and a_x an exponent specific to each x . By expressing the equations of mass, momentum and energy conservation with the variables of the system $\bar{\Sigma}$, then by substituting the \bar{x} by $b^{a_x} x$, the latter equations become:

$$b^{a_\rho - a_t} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + b^{a_\rho + a_v - a_r} \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{v}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$b^{a_\rho + a_v - a_t} \frac{\partial (\rho \vec{v})}{\partial t} + b^{a_\rho + 2a_v - a_r} \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}) + b^{a_P - a_r} \vec{\nabla} P + b^{2a_B - a_\mu - a_r} \left[\vec{\nabla} \left(\frac{B^2}{2\mu} \right) - \frac{1}{\mu} (\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B} \right] = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$b^{a_P - a_t} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + b^{a_P + a_v - a_r} \vec{\nabla} \cdot (P \vec{v}) + b^{a_\gamma + a_P + a_v - a_r} \gamma P \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} - b^{a_P + a_v - a_r} P \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \quad (11)$$

Note that equation (11) is not quite the one given in section A.5.3, but rather the internal energy conservation equation (97) given in section A.1.4, multiplied by $(\gamma - 1)$. This form makes it easier to justify the invariance of γ in the following. Now it is possible to study the invariance conditions of equations (9), (10) and (11). For the equation (9) to be identical to the one expressed with the variables x , it is necessary to impose that $b^{a_\rho - a_t} = b^{a_\rho + a_v - a_r}$, and therefore $a_t + a_v - a_r = 0$. This condition results in $tv/r = \bar{t}\bar{v}/\bar{r}$. Thus, the first invariant of the transformation obtained with this method is $I_1 = tv/r$. Equations (10) and (11) give the additional invariants $I_2 = \rho v^2/P$, $I_3 = B^2/(P\mu)$ and $I_4 = \gamma$. The other equations of the ideal MHD do not provide more invariants than those obtainable by combinations of those already found.

The quantities, used in the dimensionless numbers I_i obtained so far, are naturally those appearing in the equations of the model. To add other physical quantities, it is possible to apply the method on other equations. Thus, the equation of state of the ideal plasma, and the one giving its internal energy, both given in section A.2.2, are used to define additional invariants containing T and U . Note that V the volume is intrinsic to each geometry, and that the number density n can be replaced by ρ/m with m the mass (kg) of a particle. The equation of state of the ideal plasma gives the invariant $I_5 = Pm/(\rho T)$. The expression of the internal energy in the volume related to each geometry gives $I_6 = Pr^3/U$ (in the point source geometry), $I'_6 = Pr^2 L_c/U$ (in the line source geometry) and $I''_6 = Pr L_c^2/U$ (in the plane source geometry). Now, since the evolution of the blast wave is parameterized by the initial conditions, the quantities v , ρ , P , B , T and U are replaced respectively by v_0 , ρ_0 , P_0 , B_0 , T_0 and U_d . A summary of the invariants found is proposed in table 5a.

It is possible to combine I_1 and I_2 so that only one of them contains v_0 . And since v_0 is zero, the invariant that contains it could be forgotten. Also, since the temperature is not essential to the description of the system, it would be possible to suppress I_5 . These simplifications would result in four invariants, as for the dimensional analysis performed in section 2.1.1. On the other hand, as shown in table 5b, all the dimensionless numbers N_j from section 2.1.1 can be expressed from combinations of the invariants I_i . Thus, the same

i	I_i
1^*	$\frac{tv_0}{r}$
2^*	$\frac{\rho_0 v_0^2}{P_0}$
3^*	$\frac{B_0^2}{P_0 \mu_0}$
4^*	γ
5^*	$\frac{P_0 m}{\rho_0 T_0}$
6	$\frac{P_0 r^3}{U_d}$
$6'$	$\frac{P_0 r^2 L_c}{U_d}$
$6''$	$\frac{P_0 r L_c^2}{U_d}$

(a) Scale transformation invariants.

N_1^*	I_4^*
N_4^*	I_3^*
N_6^*	I_6^*
N_7	$(I_1^*)^6 (I_2^*)^3 (I_6)^2$
N_7'	$(I_1^*)^4 (I_2^*)^2 (I_6')^2$
N_7''	$(I_1^*)^2 (I_2^*)^1 (I_6'')^2$

 (b) Correspondences with the N_i^* from section 2.1.1.

Table 5: Recap on invariants.

dimensionless numbers can be obtained with the dimensional analysis method and the invariance of equations method. However, the second method is more systematic in the sense that, once the model is chosen, the relevant physical quantities follow naturally from the equations, and the meaning of the dimensionless numbers thus obtained is less opaque than when the quantities are combined quite arbitrarily on the sole basis of their dimension.

2.2 Preliminary study without magnetic field

2.2.1 Taylor-von Neumann-Sedov blast wave

In order to start the study from known results, it is assumed at first that the magnetic field is zero. In this simplified problem, a strong explosion still releases a large amount of energy U_d in a small volume during a short time interval. In point source geometry, this will create a strong spherical shock wave propagating outwards from the explosion center. The problem then becomes similar to the one described by Taylor [4], von Neumann [5] and Sedov [6], generally called the Taylor-von Neumann-Sedov (TNS) blast wave. These authors supposed that the pressure behind the blast wave, i.e. in the region where the energy has been released, remains very large in comparison with the pressure P_0 ahead of the blast wave. To describe the blast wave they only kept as physical quantities the energy released by the explosion U_d , the mass density ρ_0 , the radius of the blast wave r and the elapsed time since the explosion t . The only one non-dimensional combination available for these four parameters is $U_d^1 \rho_0^{-1} t^2 r^{-5}$. This allowed them to come up with a solution from the dimensional analysis for the position $r(t)$ of the blast wave front. With β a constant, the solution is written:

$$\text{(Point source solution)} \quad r(t) = \beta \left(\frac{U_d}{\rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{5}} t^{\frac{2}{5}} \quad (12)$$

This law, resulting from the dimensional analysis can be generalized in the other geometries. To describe the blast wave in the line source geometry, the physical quantities to be kept are: the energy per unit length U_d/L_c

released by the explosion, the mass density ρ_0 , the radius of the blast wave r and the elapsed time since the explosion t . The only one non-dimensional combination available for these four parameters is $(U_d/L_c)^1 \rho_0^{-1} t^2 r^{-4}$. This leads to a line source version of the TNS solution, which is written:

$$\text{(Line source solution)} \quad r(t) = \beta' \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} t^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (13)$$

In the plane source geometry the physical quantities to keep are the energy per unit area U_d/L_c^2 released by the explosion, the mass density ρ_0 , the radius of the blast wave r and the elapsed time since the explosion t . The only one non-dimensional combination available for these four parameters is $(U_d/L_c^2)^1 \rho_0^{-1} t^2 r^{-3}$. This leads to the plane source version of the TNS solution:

$$\text{(Plane source solution)} \quad r(t) = \beta'' \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c^2 \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} t^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (14)$$

As expected, the exponent of time has its smallest value for the point source geometry as the blast wave expands in a three dimensional space, whereas for the line source geometry and plane source geometry, the blast wave propagates respectively in a two dimensional and a one dimensional space. The coefficients β , β' and β'' can be determined from the conservation of energy [8]. They depend on the geometry and γ . Their value is expressed by an integral and must be calculated numerically, but it is close to 1. For example, with $\gamma = 7/5$, $\beta = 1.033$ in the point source geometry.

2.2.2 Zel'dovich-Raizer approximate treatment

Zel'dovich and Raizer make the hypothesis that the mass contained in the volume V_{BW} encompassed by the blast wave (BW) is concentrated in a thin layer close to the blast wave front [9]. Then, using Newton's second law on that layer, and an energy balance in V_{BW} , they obtain a very good approximation of the coefficient β for the point source geometry. The approach adopted by Zel'dovich and Raizer is extended here to the other geometries studied in the problem. Thus, it is noted respectively β_{ZR} , β'_{ZR} and β''_{ZR} , the approximate coefficient of β , β' and β'' . The Zel'dovich-Raizer (ZR) approximation is written in the three geometries:

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad \beta_{ZR} = \left(\frac{75}{16\pi} \frac{(\gamma-1)(\gamma+1)^2}{3\gamma-1} \right)^{\frac{1}{5}} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad \beta'_{ZR} = \left(\frac{4}{\pi} \frac{(\gamma-1)(\gamma+1)^2}{3\gamma-1} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad \beta''_{ZR} = \left(\frac{9}{8} \frac{(\gamma-1)(\gamma+1)^2}{3\gamma-1} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (17)$$

In the energy balance, Zel'dovich and Raizer introduce a coefficient noted α to express the average pressure in the volume V_{BW} encompassed by the blast wave from the pressure P_1 in the thin layer that concentrates the matter. The average pressure in V_{BW} is then given by αP_1 . It turns out that, in the strong shock hypothesis, this coefficient α has the same value in all geometries of the problem:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{2} \quad (18)$$

2.2.3 Blast wave front characterization

This section deals with the behavior of physical quantities in the vicinity of the blast wave front, in a non-magnetized plasma. To describe the discontinuity of variables at the front, the Rankine-Hugoniot (RH) jump conditions are used. These equations are given in appendix A.1.5. They can be derived from the Euler equations given in appendix A.1.3. The specific enthalpy in the equation for energy conservation must be replaced by its expression for an ideal gas (see appendix A.2.2).

Here, the subscript 1 corresponds to the state of the plasma on the side disturbed by the blast wave. The subscript 2 corresponds to the state of the plasma on the side of the undisturbed space. Finally, the subscript n refers to the normal component with respect to the blast wave front. The speeds are expressed in the reference frame of the blast wave. In the latter, the front of the blast wave is immobile, and the speed $v_{n,2}$ of the plasma on the side 2 is equal to the opposite of the speed dr/dt of the blast wave front in the reference frame of the star. It should also be noted that the quantities ρ_2 and P_2 , are respectively equal to the quantities ρ_0 and P_0 of the initial plasma. The equation of conservation of mass shows the equality of the ratios in the equation below. The dimensionless quantity \mathcal{X} is introduced to note the value of these ratios:

$$\frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} = \frac{v_{n,2}}{v_{n,1}} = \mathcal{X} \quad (19)$$

To get more information about the value of \mathcal{X} , the three RH jump conditions must be combined. Using the equation for mass conservation, $v_{n,1}$ can be expressed as a function of ρ_2 , ρ_1 and $v_{n,2}$. By injecting the expression of $v_{n,1}$ in the equation for momentum conservation, P_1 can be expressed as a function of P_2 , ρ_2 , ρ_1 and $v_{n,2}$. Finally, by injecting the expression of P_1 in the equation for energy conservation, by substituting $v_{n,1}$ by its expression, and by making the Mach number M appear, the following polynomial can be obtained:

$$(\mathcal{X} - 1) \left[-\mathcal{X} \left(\gamma - 1 + \frac{2}{M^2} \right) + \gamma + 1 \right] = 0 \quad (20)$$

A simple solution of equation (20) is $\mathcal{X} = 1$. But the latter solution is not interesting in the context of a blast wave since it is not representative of a discontinuity. The other solution of equation (20) is given by:

$$\mathcal{X} = \frac{\gamma + 1}{\gamma - 1 + \frac{2}{M^2}} \quad (21)$$

A blast wave is characterized, at least in the absence of a magnetic field, by a very large Mach number. Thus, by neglecting M^{-2} in equation (21), it is possible to obtain the following relation:

$$\mathcal{X} = \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} = \frac{v_{n,2}}{v_{n,1}} = \frac{\gamma + 1}{\gamma - 1} \quad (22)$$

For a monoatomic ideal gas ($\gamma = 5/3$), the matter is compressed by a factor $\mathcal{X} = 4$ at the blast wave front, provided the condition $M \gg 1$. For a diatomic ideal gas ($\gamma = 7/5$), it would be compressed by a factor $\mathcal{X} = 6$ under the same condition. However, as the blast wave progresses, its speed decreases. With time it is to be expected that the compression ratio will decrease and tend towards 1.

2.2.4 Conversion to sound wave

The most immediate way to obtain the TNS solution is to proceed by dimensional analysis, as shown in section 2.2.1. The purpose of the present section is, on the one hand, to show another way to justify the TNS solution, and on the other hand, to propose an analytical model describing the progressive conversion of the blast wave into a sound wave (SW). The approach is to estimate the velocity of the blast wave front using the jump condition for momentum conservation and a simplified energy balance. Using the quantity \mathcal{X} introduced previously, it is possible to put the RH equation for momentum conservation in the following form:

$$v_{n,2}^2 = \frac{\mathcal{X}}{\mathcal{X} - 1} \frac{P_1 - P_2}{\rho_2} \quad (23)$$

Moreover, an energy balance can be made in the volume V_{BW} encompassed by the blast wave front. As in the ZR approximate solution in section 2.2.2, a coefficient α is introduced to express the average pressure in the volume V_{BW} from the pressure P_1 . The average pressure in V_{BW} is then given by αP_1 and the energy balance in V_{BW} is written:

$$U_d + P_2 \frac{V_{BW}}{\gamma - 1} = \alpha P_1 \frac{V_{BW}}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{1}{2} \rho_2 V_{BW} (v_{n,1} - v_{n,2})^2 \quad (24)$$

The left-hand side of equation (24) corresponds to the state of the system at $t = t_0$. In V_{BW} , the deposited energy U_d raised the pressure from P_2 to αP_1 , and set in motion the matter at a speed $v_{n,1} - v_{n,2}$ (in the reference frame of the star), leaving the system in a state described by the right-hand side of the equation. By manipulating this energy balance it is possible to obtain the expression of the pressure P_1 :

$$P_1 = \frac{\gamma - 1}{\alpha} \frac{U_d}{V_{BW}} - \frac{\gamma - 1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\mathcal{X}} - 1 \right)^2 \frac{1}{2} \rho_2 v_{n,2}^2 + \frac{P_2}{\alpha} \quad (25)$$

As a reminder, $v_{n,2} = -dr/dt$, $P_2 = P_0$ and $\rho_2 = \rho_0$. Inserting the expression of P_1 , derived from equation (25), in equation (23), allows to obtain the following equation:

$$\left(\frac{dr}{dt} \right)^2 = f_1(t) \frac{U_d}{\rho_0 V_{BW}} + f_2(t) \frac{P_0}{\rho_0} \quad (26)$$

with:

$$f_1(t) = \frac{2\mathcal{X}^2(\gamma - 1)}{2\alpha\mathcal{X}(\mathcal{X} - 1) + (\gamma - 1)(\mathcal{X} - 1)^2} \quad (27)$$

$$f_2(t) = \frac{2\mathcal{X}^2(1 - \alpha)}{2\alpha\mathcal{X}(\mathcal{X} - 1) + (\gamma - 1)(\mathcal{X} - 1)^2} \quad (28)$$

The functions f_1 and f_2 depend on time. But to simplify equation (26), the hypothesis that will be made is that f_1 and f_2 can be considered as constant without affecting too much the accuracy of the model. The arguments that justify this assumption are the following. With increasing time, the volume V_{BW} diverges. Thus, after a sufficiently long time, the quantity U_d/V_{BW} becomes much lower than P_0 , and the value of f_1 is not important in (26) as long as the term containing P_0 prevails. On the other hand, for a time t close to t_0 , the volume V_{BW} tends towards 0. Then, the quantity U_d/V_{BW} becomes much larger than P_0 , and the value of f_2 is not important in (26) as long as the term containing U_d/V_{BW} prevails. Thus, it is reasonable to assume $f_1(t) = f_1(0)$ and $f_2(t) = f_2(\infty)$.

Now, to determine the value of $f_1(0)$ and $f_2(\infty)$, it is possible to use the fact that, for $t \rightarrow 0$, the solution must correspond to the TNS blast wave, and for $t \rightarrow \infty$, the wave must propagate at the speed of sound. When $t \rightarrow t_0$, the ZR approximation gives the value of α in equation (18), and equation (21) gives $\mathcal{X} \rightarrow (\gamma + 1)/(\gamma - 1)$. Using these values of \mathcal{X} and α in equation (27) at $t = t_0$, and equation (3) at $t \rightarrow \infty$, the constants $f_1(0)$ and $f_2(\infty)$ take the following expressions:

$$f_1(0) = \frac{(\gamma - 1)(\gamma + 1)^2}{3\gamma - 1} \quad (29)$$

$$f_2(\infty) = \gamma \quad (30)$$

By replacing $f_1(t)$ by $f_1(0)$, $f_2(t)$ by $f_2(\infty)$, V_{BW} by $(4/3)\pi r^3$ (in the point source geometry), $L_c \pi r^2$ (in the line source geometry), U_d/r^2 (in the plane source geometry), and by making the coefficient β_{ZR}^* appear, equation (26) becomes in the three geometries:

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad \frac{dr}{dt} = \left(\frac{4}{25} \beta_{ZR}^5 \frac{U_d}{\rho_0} r^{-3} + v_s^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (31)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad \frac{dr}{dt} = \left(\frac{1}{4} \beta_{ZR}'^4 \frac{U_d}{L_c \rho_0} r^{-2} + v_s^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (32)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad \frac{dr}{dt} = \left(\frac{4}{9} \beta_{ZR}''^3 \frac{U_d}{L_c^2 \rho_0} r^{-1} + v_s^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (33)$$

Equations (31), (32) and (33) are differential equations for $r(t)$. The initial condition $r = 0$ is imposed at $t = t_0$. While equation (32) provides a simple solution, giving the position of the blast wave front over time,

the solutions provided by equations (31) and (33) are more complicated. The latter give the time as a function of the radius and require the use of the hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1$ and the inverse hyperbolic sine \sinh^{-1} :

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad t = \left(\frac{r^5 \rho_0}{\beta_{ZR}^5 U_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} {}_2F_1 \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{6}, \frac{11}{6}, -\frac{25}{4} \frac{r^3 \rho_0 v_s^2}{\beta_{ZR}^5 U_d} \right) \quad (34)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad r = \left[\beta_{ZR}'^2 \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} t + (v_s t)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (35)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad t = \left(\frac{\Psi r}{v_s^4} + \frac{r^2}{v_s^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{\Psi}{v_s^3} \sinh^{-1} \left(v_s \sqrt{\frac{r}{\Psi}} \right) \quad (36)$$

with:

$$\Psi = \frac{4}{9} \beta_{ZR}''^3 \frac{U_d}{L_c^2 \rho_0} \quad (37)$$

Neglecting the initial pressure P_0 (like in the TNS model), means neglecting the speed of sound v_s , as shown in equation (3). Assuming $v_s = 0$ in equations (31), (32) and (33), leads to the same solutions as those presented in sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. Therefore, the TNS solutions can be found with the method used in this section. Moreover, this approach allows to analytically approximate the behavior of the blast wave during its transition into a SW.

In section 3.3, it will be shown that equations (34), (35) and (36) allow to predict quite accurately the simulated radius $r(t)$ of the blast wave in the domain where the pressure P_0 can no longer be neglected, and therefore, where the TNS solution does not apply anymore. Having allowed a generalization, this method will then be reiterated in the following, by taking this time the magnetic field into account.

2.2.5 Transition characteristic quantities

It is now well established that, in the assumptions of the problem, the blast wave will begin its progression by following the TNS solution, and will end its course as a SW. The analytical models developed in the previous section give the gradual transition between these two asymptotic regimes ($t \rightarrow 0$ and $t \rightarrow \infty$). The question that now arises is at what characteristic distance and time the transition from the TNS regime to the SW regime occurs.

Equations (31), (32) and (33) show that the speed of the blast wave is a combination of the speeds related to the two asymptotic regimes. The problem assumptions imply that $f_1(0)U_d/(\rho_0 V_{BW})$ is initially much greater than v_s^2 . Over time, $f_1(0)U_d/(\rho_0 V_{BW})$ decreases and becomes smaller than v_s^2 . The transition between the two regimes occurs when these two quantities are comparable. That is to say when the speed given by the ZR solution is of the order of magnitude of the speed of sound in the medium. Imposing the equality of these two quantities reveals the expression of a radius r_{SW} characteristic of the transition into a SW in each geometry:

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad r_{SW} = \left(\frac{4}{25} \frac{\beta_{ZR}^5 U_d}{v_s^2 \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \approx \left(\frac{U_d}{P_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (38)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad r_{SW} = \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\beta_{ZR}'^4 U_d}{v_s^2 L_c \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \approx \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c P_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (39)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad r_{SW} = \frac{4}{9} \frac{\beta_{ZR}''^3 U_d}{v_s^2 L_c^2 \rho_0} \approx \frac{U_d}{L_c^2 P_0} \quad (40)$$

It can be noticed that this characteristic radius can be found in different ways, ignoring a multiplication factor of the order of the unit. First by setting $N_6^* = 1$, or $I_6^* = 1$. Second, by asking that the pressure $P_1 \approx U_d/V_{BW}$ at the blast wave front be equal to the pressure P_0 . Now, let t_{SW} be the time characteristic of the transition into a SW, such that $r(t_{SW}) = r_{SW}$. Since in the first phase, the solution is similar to the TNS solution, the time t_{SW} can be expressed thanks to the ZR solution:

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad t_{SW} = \left(\frac{r_{SW}}{\beta_{ZR}} \right)^{\frac{5}{2}} \left(\frac{\rho_0}{U_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \approx U_d^{\frac{1}{3}} \frac{\rho_0^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P_0^{\frac{5}{6}}} \quad (41)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad t_{SW} = \left(\frac{r_{SW}}{\beta_{ZR}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{L_c \rho_0}{U_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \approx \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\rho_0^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P_0} \quad (42)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad t_{SW} = \left(\frac{r_{SW}}{\beta_{ZR}} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{L_c^2 \rho_0}{U_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \approx \frac{U_d}{L_c^2} \frac{\rho_0^{\frac{1}{2}}}{P_0^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (43)$$

2.3 Addition of an ambient magnetic field

2.3.1 Blast wave front characterization

The addition of a magnetic field to the problem changes the RH jump conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to study again the behavior of the physical quantities near the front of the blast wave. The RH jump conditions for MHD are given in appendix A.5.4.

As before, the subscript 1 corresponds to the state of the plasma on the side disturbed by the blast wave, and the subscript 2 corresponds to the state of the plasma on the side of the undisturbed space. The subscripts t and n refer respectively to the tangential and normal components of a vector, with respect to the blast wave front. The quantities are expressed in the reference frame of the blast wave.

It is assumed that the blast wave front propagates perpendicular to the magnetic field $\vec{B}_0 = B_0 \vec{u}_z$. This is the case in the plane source geometry, in the line source geometry, and in the plane of symmetry of the point source geometry. Thus, on the side of the undisturbed space, $B_{t,2} = B_0$ and $B_{n,2} = 0$. The continuity of the normal component of \vec{B} , and the conservation of mass, imply the equality of the ratios in the equation below. As in the problem without magnetic field, these ratios are noted \mathcal{X} :

$$\frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} = \frac{v_{n,2}}{v_{n,1}} = \frac{B_{t,1}}{B_{t,2}} = \mathcal{X} \quad (44)$$

To determine the value of \mathcal{X} , all the RH equations for MHD must be combined. This time it is a third-degree polynomial that is obtained, instead of (20). In addition to the Mach number M , the Alfvén number A also appears naturally due to the presence of the magnetic field:

$$(\mathcal{X} - 1) \left[\mathcal{X}^2 (\gamma - 2) \frac{1}{A^2} - \mathcal{X} \left(\gamma - 1 + \frac{\gamma}{A^2} + \frac{2}{M^2} \right) + \gamma + 1 \right] = 0 \quad (45)$$

Equation (45) has three solutions. Once again, the constant solution equal to a 1 can be discarded since it is not representative of a shock. Among the two remaining roots, there is one that diverges with increasing A . However, based on the solution (21) given in section 2.2.3, the value of \mathcal{X} must converge when the ambient magnetic field tends to 0, and thus, by definition, when A tends to infinity. This solution is therefore also discarded. The remaining solution, illustrated in figure 5, is written:

$$\mathcal{X} = \frac{\gamma - 1 + \gamma \frac{1}{A^2} + 2 \frac{1}{M^2} - \sqrt{\left(\gamma - 1 + \gamma \frac{1}{A^2} + 2 \frac{1}{M^2} \right)^2 - 4(\gamma - 2)(\gamma + 1) \frac{1}{A^2}}}{2(\gamma - 2) \frac{1}{A^2}} \quad (46)$$

This new solution is not as simple as the one given in equation (21), but it reduces to the latter when A tends to infinity. By removing the factor $(\mathcal{X} - 1)$ from equation (45), and by imposing $\mathcal{X} = 1$, the equality $A^{-2} + M^{-2} = 1$ appears. On the other hand, if γ were equal to 2, i.e. equal to γ_B (see section 1.2.5), the expression of \mathcal{X} would take a much simpler form, and would then depend only on the parameter $A^{-2} + M^{-2}$. Thus, the complexity of the expression of \mathcal{X} can be attributed to the difference in value between the heat capacity ratio γ and its magnetic counterpart γ_B . Nevertheless, it remains that when both M and A are very large compared to 1 the same solution as in equation (22) is found:

$$\mathcal{X} = \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} = \frac{v_{n,2}}{v_{n,1}} = \frac{B_{t,1}}{B_{t,2}} = \frac{\gamma + 1}{\gamma - 1} \quad (47)$$

Figure 5: Quantity \mathcal{X} as a function of the inverse of the Mach number and the inverse of the Alfvén number.

2.3.2 Conversion to magnetosonic wave

This section aims to reapply the approach presented in section 2.2.4. As in the previous section, it is assumed that the blast wave propagates perpendicular to the magnetic field $\vec{B}_0 = B_0 \vec{u}_z$. Using the quantity \mathcal{X} from the previous section, the RH jump condition for momentum conservation in MHD can be written as follows:

$$v_{n,2}^2 = \frac{\mathcal{X}}{\mathcal{X} - 1} \frac{P_1 - P_2}{\rho_2} + \mathcal{X}(\mathcal{X} + 1) \frac{B_{t,2}^2}{2\mu\rho_2} \quad (48)$$

This time, the energy balance in the volume V_{BW} encompassed by the blast wave must also include the electromagnetic energy. The average pressure in V_{BW} is still given by αP_1 . In order to express the average magnetic pressure in V_{BW} , another coefficient α_B is introduced. Thus, the average magnetic pressure in V_{BW} is given by $\alpha_B B_{t,1}^2 / (2\mu)$. The energy balance is then written:

$$U_d + P_2 \frac{V_{BW}}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{B_{t,2}^2}{2\mu} V_{BW} = \alpha P_1 \frac{V_{BW}}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{1}{2} \rho_2 V_{BW} (v_{n,1} - v_{n,2})^2 + \alpha_B \frac{B_{t,1}^2}{2\mu} V_{BW} \quad (49)$$

The left-hand side of equation (49) corresponds to the state of the system at $t = t_0$. In V_{BW} , the deposited energy U_d raised the pressure from P_2 to αP_1 , raised the magnetic pressure from $B_{t,2}^2 / (2\mu)$ to $\alpha_B B_{t,1}^2 / (2\mu)$, and set in motion the matter at a speed $v_{n,1} - v_{n,2}$ (in the reference frame of the star), leaving the system in a state described by the right-hand side of the equation. By manipulating this energy balance, it is possible to obtain the expression of the pressure P_1 :

$$P_1 = \frac{\gamma - 1}{\alpha} \frac{U_d}{V_{BW}} - \frac{\gamma - 1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\mathcal{X}} - 1 \right)^2 \frac{1}{2} \rho_2 v_{n,2}^2 + \frac{P_2}{\alpha} + \frac{\gamma - 1}{\alpha} (1 - \alpha_B \mathcal{X}^2) \frac{B_{t,2}^2}{2\mu} \quad (50)$$

Inserting the expression of P_1 from equation (50) in equation (48), and using the relations $v_{n,2} = -dr/dt$, $P_2 = P_0$, $\rho_2 = \rho_0$, $B_{t,2} = B_0$ and $\mu = \mu_0$, allows to obtain the following equation:

$$\left(\frac{dr}{dt} \right)^2 = f_1(t) \frac{U_d}{\rho_0 V_{BW}} + f_2(t) \frac{P_0}{\rho_0} + f_3(t) \frac{B_0^2}{2\mu_0 \rho_0} \quad (51)$$

with f_1 and f_2 given in equations (27) and (28), and:

$$f_3(t) = \frac{2\mathcal{X}^2(\gamma - 1)(1 - \alpha_B\mathcal{X}^2) + 2\alpha\mathcal{X}^3(\mathcal{X}^2 - 1)}{2\alpha\mathcal{X}(\mathcal{X} - 1) + (\gamma - 1)(\mathcal{X} - 1)^2} \quad (52)$$

As f_1 and f_2 , the function f_3 depends on time. To simplify equation (51), f_1 , f_2 and f_3 will be considered as constant. The arguments that justify this assumption are similar to those advanced in section 2.2.4. With increasing time, the volume V_{BW} diverges. Thus, after a sufficiently long time, the quantity U_d/V_{BW} becomes much lower than P_0 and $B_0^2/(2\mu_0)$, and the value of f_1 is not important in (51) as long as the terms containing P_0 and $B_0^2/(2\mu_0)$ prevail. On the other hand, for a time t close to t_0 , the volume V_{BW} tends towards 0. Then, the quantity U_d/V_{BW} becomes much larger than P_0 and $B_0^2/(2\mu_0)$, and the values of f_2 and f_3 are not important in (51) as long as the term containing U_d/V_{BW} prevails. It is therefore assumed $f_1(t) = f_1(0)$, $f_2(t) = f_2(\infty)$ and $f_3(t) = f_3(\infty)$.

As in the case without magnetic field, the value of $f_1(0)$ is given in equation (29). What changes this time is that the blast wave becomes a fast magnetosonic wave (FMW) whose speed v_{FMW} is equal to $\sqrt{v_s^2 + v_A^2}$ in the direction perpendicular to the magnetic field \vec{B}_0 , as explained in section A.5.5. This allows to find the same value of $f_2(\infty)$ as the one given in equation (30), but also to express $f_3(\infty)$:

$$f_3(\infty) = 2 = \gamma_B \quad (53)$$

By replacing $f_1(t)$, $f_2(t)$ and $f_3(t)$ by their associated constants, V_{BW} by $(4/3)\pi r^3$ (in the point source geometry), $L_c\pi r^2$ (in the line source geometry), U_d/r^2 (in the plane source geometry), and by making the coefficient β_{ZR}^* appear, equation (51) is declined as follows in the three geometries:

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad \frac{dr}{dt} = \left(\frac{4}{25}\beta_{ZR}^5 \frac{U_d}{\rho_0} r^{-3} + v_{FMW}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (54)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad \frac{dr}{dt} = \left(\frac{1}{4}\beta_{ZR}'^4 \frac{U_d}{L_c\rho_0} r^{-2} + v_{FMW}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (55)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad \frac{dr}{dt} = \left(\frac{4}{9}\beta_{ZR}''^3 \frac{U_d}{L_c^2\rho_0} r^{-1} + v_{FMW}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (56)$$

Equations (54), (55) and (56) are respectively almost identical to equations (31), (32) and (33). Thus, without much astonishment, the solutions take very similar forms with the initial conditions $r = 0$ at $t = t_0$, with Ψ given in (37):

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad t = \left(\frac{r^5\rho_0}{\beta_{ZR}^5 U_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} {}_2F_1 \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{6}, \frac{11}{6}, -\frac{25}{4} \frac{r^3\rho_0 v_{FMW}^2}{\beta_{ZR}^5 U_d} \right) \quad (57)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad r = \left[\beta_{ZR}'^2 \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c\rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} t + (v_{FMW}t)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (58)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad t = \left(\frac{\Psi r}{v_{FMW}^4} + \frac{r^2}{v_{FMW}^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{\Psi}{v_{FMW}^3} \sinh^{-1} \left(v_{FMW} \sqrt{\frac{r}{\Psi}} \right) \quad (59)$$

The model was developed for a blast wave propagating in a direction perpendicular to the magnetic field \vec{B}_0 . In this case it is correct to replace $v_s^2 + v_A^2$ by v_{FMW}^2 as it has been done. However, the equations obtained do not, a priori, cover the entire problem in the point source geometry, because for other directions it is no longer possible to consider $v_{FMW}^2 = v_s^2 + v_A^2$. To generalize the model, it is simply assumed that equations (54), (55) and (56) are valid for all directions, and that therefore the expression of v_{FMW} depends on the angle θ between the direction of propagation and the magnetic field. This generalization does not follow directly from the analytical justification proposed above, but rather from the argument that the blast wave must transform into a FMW, whatever the direction.

2.3.3 Transition characteristic quantities

The same reasoning as that used in section 2.2.5 is applied here to identify quantities characterizing the transition from the TNS regime to the FMW regime. Thus, the transition radius r_{FMW} , this time based on equations (57), (58) and (59), is written in each geometry:

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad r_{FMW} = \left(\frac{4}{25} \frac{\beta_{ZR}^5 U_d}{v_{FMW}^2 \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (60)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad r_{FMW} = \left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{\beta'_{ZR}{}^4 U_d}{v_{FMW}^2 L_c \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (61)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad r_{FMW} = \frac{4}{9} \frac{\beta''_{ZR}{}^3 U_d}{v_{FMW}^2 L_c^2 \rho_0} \quad (62)$$

The time t_{FMW} , characteristic of the transition from the TNS regime to the FMW regime, is obtained by injecting r_{FMW} into the ZR solution. The latter is written in the three geometries:

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad t_{FMW} = \left(\frac{r_{FMW}}{\beta_{ZR}} \right)^{\frac{5}{2}} \left(\frac{\rho_0}{U_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (63)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad t_{FMW} = \left(\frac{r_{FMW}}{\beta_{ZR}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{L_c \rho_0}{U_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (64)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad t_{FMW} = \left(\frac{r_{FMW}}{\beta_{ZR}} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{L_c^2 \rho_0}{U_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (65)$$

It is noted that when the initial magnetic field \vec{B}_0 is such that the magnetic pressure P_{B_0} is much greater than the initial kinetic pressure P_0 , the transition radius r_{FMW} can be assimilated to a magnetic confinement radius r_B given by:

$$\text{(Point source)} \quad r_B \approx \left(\frac{U_d}{P_{B_0}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (66)$$

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad r_B \approx \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c P_{B_0}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (67)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad r_B \approx \frac{U_d}{L_c^2 P_{B_0}} \quad (68)$$

On the other hand, when the magnetic pressure P_{B_0} is much lower than the kinetic pressure P_0 , the FMW is similar to the SW. For this reason, the quantities r_{SW} and t_{SW} are special cases of r_{FMW} and t_{FMW} . In the same way, solutions (34), (35) and (36) are special cases of solutions (57), (58) and (59).

In the same way that the solution in point source geometry is extrapolated for directions not perpendicular to the magnetic field \vec{B}_0 in the previous section, the transition radius and time can be expressed as a function of θ using the expression for v_{FMW} given in section A.5.5. The v_{FMW} being the greatest for $\theta = 0$, it can be expected that the transition to FMW takes place later in the direction parallel to \vec{B}_0 than in the plane perpendicular to \vec{B}_0 .

2.4 Scaling laws

2.4.1 Constraints from invariants

This section aims at providing tools for the reproduction of an experiment at different scales. These tools are called scaling laws. The latter are derived from the invariants found in section 2.1.2. Let Σ be the system corresponding to an experiment of reference. This system is described by the physical quantities noted x . The scaling laws should make it possible to set the value of the quantities \bar{x} characterizing the experiment conducted in a system $\bar{\Sigma}$ at a different scale (different energy U_d , different magnetic field \bar{B}_0 , etc.), so that the two experiments are similar. The invariants, listed in table 5a, impose the following relations:

$$I_1^* = \bar{I}_1^* \iff \frac{\bar{t} \bar{v}_0}{t v_0} = \frac{\bar{r}}{r} \quad (69)$$

$$I_2^* = \bar{I}_2^* \iff \frac{\bar{\rho}_0}{\rho_0} \left(\frac{\bar{v}_0}{v_0} \right)^2 = \frac{\bar{P}_0}{P_0} \quad (70)$$

$$I_3^* = \bar{I}_3^* \iff \left(\frac{\bar{B}_0}{B_0} \right)^2 = \frac{\bar{P}_0 \bar{\mu}_0}{P_0 \mu_0} \quad (71)$$

$$I_4^* = \bar{I}_4^* \iff \frac{\bar{\gamma}}{\gamma} = 1 \quad (72)$$

$$I_5^* = \bar{I}_5^* \iff \frac{\bar{P}_0 \bar{m}}{P_0 m} = \frac{\bar{\rho}_0 \bar{T}_0}{\rho_0 T_0} \quad (73)$$

$$I_6 = \bar{I}_6 \iff \frac{\bar{P}_0}{P_0} \left(\frac{\bar{r}}{r} \right)^3 = \frac{\bar{U}_d}{U_d} \quad (74)$$

$$I'_6 = \bar{I}'_6 \iff \frac{\bar{P}_0}{P_0} \left(\frac{\bar{r}}{r} \right)^2 \frac{\bar{L}_c}{L_c} = \frac{\bar{U}_d}{U_d} \quad (75)$$

$$I''_6 = \bar{I}''_6 \iff \frac{\bar{P}_0 \bar{r}}{P_0 r} \left(\frac{\bar{L}_c}{L_c} \right)^2 = \frac{\bar{U}_d}{U_d} \quad (76)$$

Thus, in each geometry of the problem, there are six constraints and 12 variables. Before giving a value to the quantities \bar{x} , from the quantities x , it remains to define six additional constraints. These constraints can be chosen according to the objective to be reached. For example, to study astrophysical phenomena from laboratory experiments, it is possible to set the value of \bar{r}/r , \bar{t}/t , etc. from the data of the problem and the experimental means at disposal.

In the following, an application will be proposed in which the chosen constraints will be adapted for the comparison of similar laboratory experiments with lasers at different energies. Such a study will allow, on the one hand, to demonstrate the validity of the scaling laws, and on the other hand, to ensure the proper functioning of the laser facilities and measuring instruments. In this example, it will be important to ensure that the values of the initialization quantities, resulting from the transposition of a reference experiment to the different scales, are reasonable enough to be reached in the laboratory.

2.4.2 Similar experiment with different energies

The choice of the constraints proposed in the following is guided by the objective of reproducing a similar laser shot experiment with laser facilities at different energies. Even if the laser energy can differ by several orders

of magnitude from one facility to another, the size of the firing chamber remains quite similar. It is therefore appropriate to impose $\bar{t} = t$, $\bar{r} = r$ and $\bar{L}_c = L_c$. In this way, from one experiment to another, the phenomena studied will occur over similar distances and durations in the firing chamber.

The same gas will be used, so $\bar{m} = m$ and $\bar{\mu}_0 = \mu_0$. The last constraint is the value of the ratio \bar{U}_d/U_d . The latter is chosen according to the energy range available for the lasers. From the values of the quantities \bar{x} , it is now possible to set the value of the quantities \bar{x} thanks to the scaling laws given in table 6, and derived from equations (69) to (76). Note that after applying the additional constraints $\bar{r} = r$ and $\bar{L}_c = L_c$, the scaling laws resulting from invariant I_6^* , formulated in equations (74), (75) and (76), take the same form for each geometry. Thus, the scaling laws proposed in table 6 are valid regardless of the geometry chosen.

\bar{t}/t	\bar{r}/r	\bar{L}_c/L_c	$\bar{\rho}_0/\rho_0$	\bar{P}_0/P_0	\bar{B}_0/B_0	\bar{T}_0/T_0	\bar{v}_0/v_0	$\bar{\mu}_0/\mu_0$	\bar{m}/m	$\bar{\gamma}/\gamma$
1	1	1	\bar{U}_d/U_d	\bar{U}_d/U_d	$\sqrt{\bar{U}_d/U_d}$	\bar{U}_d/U_d	1	1	1	1

Table 6: Scaling laws.

The values of the energy U_d deposited in the explosive core by the different lasers are chosen to be 1 kJ, 10 kJ, 100 kJ and 1 MJ. The four systems associated with the previous energies will be noted respectively \mathcal{A} , \mathcal{B} , \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} . Let L_Σ be the size of the firing chamber. It is assumed that the phenomena occurring just after the laser shot can be measured within a space equivalent to a one meter cube. Thus $L_\Sigma = 1$ m for all experiments.

Knowing the values of U_d and L_Σ , the pressure P_0 can be chosen so that the blast wave follows the TNS solution and does not transform into a sound wave on its course. For this, the radius r_{SW} , expressed in equation (38) for the point source geometry, must be larger than $L_\Sigma/2$. Then is fixed ρ_0 so that by taking nitrogen, or more simply air, the temperature of the gas is initially about 300 K. With the previous parameters, it is now possible to express the radius r of the blast wave in the point source geometry as a function of time using the TNS solution. This allows to define an experiment duration t_Σ such that, after a time t_Σ , the blast wave has covered an appreciable distance of the measured space, but has not yet reached the edges.

The distance L_c , which determines the density of the deposited energy in the point source and line source geometries, can be chosen so that the blast wave reaches a radius similar to the point source geometry after a time t_Σ . For this, it is possible to compare the radius given by the TNS solution in the different geometries. Finally, it remains to add (or not) an ambient magnetic field. Here, the magnetic field \vec{B}_0 will be taken so that the radius r_{FMW} , given in section 2.3.3, is smaller than $L_\Sigma/2$. This will allow to observe the phase of conversion from the blast wave to the FMW. This approach leads to the choice of parameters (valid in all geometries) presented in table 7.

Σ	U_d (J)	t_Σ (s)	L_Σ (m)	L_c (m)	r_c (m)	ρ_0 (kg/m ³)	P_0 (Pa)	P_{B_0} (Pa)	B_0 (T)
\mathcal{A}	1.0×10^3	1.0×10^{-4}	1.0	0.2	1.25×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-2}	1.0×10^3	1.0×10^5	≈ 0.50
\mathcal{B}	1.0×10^4	1.0×10^{-4}	1.0	0.2	1.25×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-1}	1.0×10^4	1.0×10^6	≈ 1.59
\mathcal{C}	1.0×10^5	1.0×10^{-4}	1.0	0.2	1.25×10^{-2}	1.0×10^0	1.0×10^5	1.0×10^7	≈ 5.01
\mathcal{D}	1.0×10^6	1.0×10^{-4}	1.0	0.2	1.25×10^{-2}	1.0×10^1	1.0×10^6	1.0×10^8	≈ 15.85

Table 7: Value of the parameters at the different scales.

The different experiments proposed in this section will be simulated in the following with the MHD program CLOVIS. It will then be possible to verify the predictions of the scaling laws given in table 6.

3 Numerical approach

3.1 Computer programs

3.1.1 CLOVIS

The program CLOVIS is used to simulate the blast wave resulting from the deposit of energy in the explosive core. It is an aid to the understanding of the physical phenomena involved, and a means of testing analytical models. It implements the finite volume method (FVM) with formula translation (FORTRAN) to solve the partial differential equations of MHD. The solver used is the Harten-Lax-van Leer discontinuities (HLLD) [10, 11], and the mesh is Cartesian. The initialization parameters of the simulations are chosen so as to correspond to experiments that can be achieved in the laboratory. In particular, the parameters t_Σ , L_Σ , L_c and r_c always take the same values as in table 7. In a first step, the remaining parameters U_d , ρ_0 , P_0 and B_0 , can be chosen in order to implement the experiment \mathcal{A} . Later on, they will be modified to also simulate experiences \mathcal{B} , \mathcal{C} , and \mathcal{D} , or to access other regimes. The boundary condition chosen is extrapolation and gravity is neglected.

The mesh size is set at $400 \times 400 \times 400$ cells for the point source geometry. A convergence test of the mesh is performed on a grid of $800 \times 800 \times 800$ cells. The number of cells in the direction \vec{u}_z for the line source geometry, or in the directions \vec{u}_z and \vec{u}_y for the plane source geometry is not determining given the invariances highlighted in section 1.2.3. The chosen way of proceeding is to adapt the number of cells in these directions so that the spatial extension of a cell is equal to that in the direction \vec{u}_x . Thus the cells are always cubes of 2.5×10^{-4} m of side. As the mesh is regular, the deposit of energy in a negligible volume raises some concerns. The energy is deposited in the form of kinetic pressure in V_c . It is found after some simulations that a good compromise is to take a radius r_c as long as five mesh cells, what gives the radius r_c proposed in table 7. Below this value, undesirable numerical effects could appear and threaten the accuracy or the convergence of the simulation. Above this value, the size of the explosive core becomes too large compared to the simulated space to be considered as a point, and a counter-shock directed towards the interior of the explosive core appears. The initialization condition thus chosen for the pressure in experiment \mathcal{A} can be seen on figure 6.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 0.0 \times 10^0 \text{ s}$$

Figure 6: Initial pressure in planes $z = 0$ and $x = 0$ of the point source geometry.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 7: Pressure in the point source geometry.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 8: Magnetic pressure and magnetic field in the point source geometry.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 9: Mass density and speed in the point source geometry.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 10: Temperature in the point source geometry.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 11: Kinetic and internal energy density in the point source geometry.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 12: Kinetic, internal and magnetic energy density in the point source geometry.

Figures 7 to 12 show different quantities describing the state of the system at a time later than the moment of the explosion. The phenomena presented in these figures are consequences of the very high pressure initialized in the explosive core illustrated in figure 6. As discussed in section 1.2.3, an angular isotropy can be seen in the plane $z = 0$. Moreover, it is possible to observe, in the plane $x = 0$, the anisotropy caused by \vec{B}_0 . Figure 7 shows that unlike the TNS solution, the kinetic pressure tends to propagate preferably in the direction of \vec{B}_0 , leaving a column that extends between two discontinuity fronts of P . Figure 8 shows on the one hand that, in the zone corresponding to the overpressure column mentioned above, the magnetic field is greatly reduced, and on the other hand that a magnetic shock propagates in directions different from that of \vec{B}_0 . Figure 9 shows the mass density and velocity. It is observed that the matter is compressed mainly at the top and bottom of the column, and to a lesser extent at the front of the magnetic shock. However, inside the column, the matter is rarefied. Plasma velocity is greatest at the top and bottom of the column. In the plane $z = 0$ it can be seen that, although the velocity is directed outward at the blast wave front, it reverses after the latter passes to point toward the center of the explosion. Figure 10 shows that the temperature follows the same trend as the kinetic pressure and density, extending along the column. However, as in the TNS model, the temperature is larger towards the center of the explosion and the BW front cannot be identified by a discontinuity. Finally, figure 12 shows the energy density corresponding to the sum of the contributions of kinetic, thermal and magnetic origins, presented separately in figures 11 and 8.

3.1.2 POSTBLAST

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 0.0 \times 10^0 \text{ s}$$

Figure 13: Pressure profiles in the point source geometry at the moment of the explosion.

CLOVIS produces three-dimensional (3D) arrays containing the values of the plasma parameters at different times. These raw data must be processed to locate and study the structure of the blast wave. POSTBLAST, a

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 14: Pressure profiles in the point source geometry.

post-processing program is developed with Python during this study to meet this need. Figures 6 to 15 are examples of illustrations generated by the latter. POSTBLAST processes the CLOVIS output files independently and in parallel. It extracts the raw data, generates new ones (such as the position of the blast wave front), then in a second phase, it conglomerates these data to generate other types of graphics containing time-dependent quantities such as figures 18 to 26. A post-processing cycle consists of two phases. The first converts hierarchical data format (HDF) files produced by CLOVIS into NPZ files that can be loaded much faster by the NumPy library for Python. The second phase generates the figures from the NPZ files. The first step is to be done only once for each simulation, while the second can be repeated as the figures are adjusted and allows to avoid the costly opening of HDF files.

The 2D cuts, presented in figures 6 to 12, show physical quantities that can be almost directly extracted from the 3D arrays produced by CLOVIS. In this representation it is difficult to quantitatively analyze the blast wave or to describe in a concise way its evolution over time. To simplify the analysis of the data, it is possible to represent the physical quantities evaluated along the axes \vec{u}_x , \vec{u}_y and \vec{u}_z . Figures 13, 14 and 15 are examples of such a representation. Figure 13 gives the profiles of the kinetic pressure in the three directions of space, and can be compared with figure 6. Figures 14 and 15 show pressure, density and magnetic field profiles at the same time as figures 7 to 12.

As shown in figure 13, the blast wave can be characterized, in its initial phase, by an important pressure discontinuity along \vec{u}_r . However, simulations show that in the directions perpendicular to the magnetic field \vec{B}_0 , the kinetic pressure jump decreases rapidly, until it is no longer, or almost no longer perceptible. Under these conditions, it becomes difficult to determine the exact location of the blast wave with only the kinetic pressure P as a variable. Figure 14 shows that a magnetic pressure discontinuity is added to the kinetic pressure

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 15: Normalized mass density and tangential magnetic field in the point source geometry.

discontinuity. The RH jump conditions for MHD, given in section A.5.4, actually indicate that kinetic pressure discontinuity and magnetic field discontinuity can go hand in hand at the blast wave front. Thus, to identify the discontinuity marking the position of the blast wave, it is the total pressure $P + P_B$ which is analysed. POSTBLAST locates the blast wave front (red dotted vertical line) where there is the greatest jump of $P + P_B$ between two consecutive mesh cells.

The radius r_{FMW} contained in figures 13, 14 and 15 is calculated from equation (60). In figure 14, outside the area bounded by the blast wave front, the total pressure $P + P_B$ is superimposed on the magnetic pressure because the initial kinetic pressure P_0 is much smaller than the initial magnetic pressure P_{B_0} . In the plane perpendicular to \vec{B}_0 , the blast wave front is characterized by a peak of the total pressure, while in the direction parallel to \vec{B}_0 , the total pressure is almost uniform. The detected position of the front indicates that the blast wave propagated less rapidly in the direction of \vec{B}_0 than in the plane perpendicular to \vec{B}_0 .

Figure 15 shows the mass density normalized by ρ_0 and the tangential magnetic field (with respect to the direction of the observed axis) normalized by B_0 . This figure confirms first of all that the matter is compressed mainly at the front in the direction parallel to \vec{B}_0 , i.e. at the top and bottom of the overpressure column as observed previously in figure 9. Using the notations introduced in section 2.3.1, it is recalled that $\rho_0 = \rho_2$ and that, in the \vec{u}_x and \vec{u}_y directions, $B_0 = B_{t,2}$. Thus, by observing that the values of ρ/ρ_0 and B_t/B_0 are equal at the top of the peak in the directions \vec{u}_x and \vec{u}_y , it is possible to confirm that equation (44) is well respected. The value of B_t/B_0 in the \vec{u}_z direction is not important because $B_{t,2}$ being null, the ratio $B_{t,1}/B_{t,2}$ is not defined anyway and therefore cannot be compared with ρ_1/ρ_2 . Finally, it is interesting to note that although \mathcal{X} is larger in the direction of the magnetic field, the blast wave propagates slower.

3.2 Validation of the simulations

3.2.1 Scaling laws

To ensure the proper functioning of CLOVIS it is proposed here to simulate the experiments designed in section 2.4.2. To do this, a total of 12 simulations, (four different scales in each of the three geometries), are prepared and executed with the parameter values defined in table 7. As predicted by the scaling laws, given in table 6, the physical phenomena simulated in systems \mathcal{B} , \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} can be compared to those simulated in system \mathcal{A} at a same time and point in space. Since the outputs from CLOVIS are periodic (in physical time, not machine time), it is natural to compare, at each time step, the output data from the four different experiments. This will allow, for example, to verify that $\rho_B = 10\rho_A$, $\rho_C = 100\rho_A$ and $\rho_D = 1000\rho_A$, at any time and point in space.

Two types of figures are proposed here to present the agreement of the simulation results and the scaling laws. For each time step and each physical quantity x among the mass density ρ , the kinetic pressure P and the magnetic pressure P_B , it is generated a first figure representing the values of x_A , x_B , x_C and x_D , and another figure presenting the values of x_B/x_A , x_C/x_A and x_D/x_A . All figures are produced with the ordinate in logarithmic scale. Thus, the scaling laws predict a constant offset between each of the curves in the first type of figure, and constant ratios of value 10, 100 and 1000 in the second type of figure. These predictions are verified in the examples given in figures 16 and 17, for the mass density ρ and the kinetic pressure P . The time selected corresponds to the one in figures 14 and 15, but it is found that the predictions from the scaling laws are fulfilled at all times. Note that even if the values of the physical quantities depend on space and time, and that their variations can be abrupt, the ratios in figure 17 remain perfectly constant.

Figure 16: Mass density profiles of the experiments defined in section 2.4.2.

Figure 17: Kinetic pressure ratios of the experiments defined in section 2.4.2.

3.2.2 TNS solution

In the following, it is noted r_{TNS} the radius given by equations (12), (13) and (14), with $\beta^* = 1$. It is also noted r_{ZR} the radius corresponding to the previous equations, but this time with $\beta^* = \beta_{ZR}^*$ from equations (15), (16) and (17). The position $r(t)$ of the simulated blast wave front having been automatically determined with POSTBLAST, it is now possible to compare the simulation results and the analytical solutions, as in the figures 18, 19 and 20. Several elements explain the choice of a log-log representation of the blast wave front position as a function of time, and the attention paid to the parallelism of the curves rather than to their superposition.

First, the log-log representation allows to evaluate the relative deviation of the analytical model and the simulation, for each time value. A constant multiplicative coefficient between the simulated position and the predicted position results in a simple offset between the curves. It is then possible to distinguish at a glance the cases where the analytical model and the simulation agree within a factor, from the cases where both diverge from each other. Given that β_{ZR} , β'_{ZR} and β''_{ZR} are approximations, it is already understandable that a slight offset may exist between the curves of the simulation and the position predicted when using the coefficients in equations (15), (16) and (17).

Moreover, the exact value of the energy actually deposited in the simulation cannot be considered as strictly equal to that declared in the initialization parameters. Indeed, the energy is deposited as pressure in the few cells constituting the explosive core. However, the calculation of this pressure P_c involves the volume V_c . In the point source geometry, this volume is ideally a sphere, but numerically it is the cells whose barycenter are located at a distance lower than r_c from O . When the size of a cell is not negligible compared to the radius r_c , the numerical volume of V_c may be a rather rough approximation of the ideal volume V_c . Thus, the amount

of energy expected and that actually deposited in the explosive core differ slightly, which is equivalent to the introduction of an unknown multiplicative coefficient in the position given by the simulation.

Therefore, it is natural to evaluate the relevance of a model first on the basis of the parallelism of the curves, and in a second step, on the proximity between the curves. Here experiment \mathcal{A} is repeated without magnetic field \vec{B}_0 and with an initial pressure P_0 low enough for the TNS phase to be observed throughout the duration of the experiment. As the TNS solution can be considered as correct under these conditions, it is more a question here of accrediting the results of simulations carried out with CLOVIS.

With regard to figures 18, 19 and 20, the simulations corroborate the analytical solutions given in equations (15), (16) and (17). Indeed the curves of the simulated position exhibit clearly the values $2/5$, $1/2$ and $2/3$ for the exponent of t . Note also that the ZR approximation, in its original form (in point source geometry), and in its generalized versions for line and plane source geometries, make it possible to obtain very precise predictions of the position of the blast wave front.

Figure 18: Simulation results and analytical model in the point source geometry without magnetic field.

Figure 19: Simulation results and analytical model in the line source geometry without magnetic field.

Figure 20: Simulation results and analytical model in the plane source geometry without magnetic field.

3.3 Validation of the analytical models

3.3.1 HD solution

Let r_{HD} be the radius from equations (34), (35) and (36). Equations (34) and (36) do not allow to express directly the radius of the blast wave front as a function of time. On the contrary, they give the time as a function of the radius, and must therefore be reversed. For a given time t , an optimization algorithm searches for the radius r such that the difference between t and the value given by the function is minimal. To provide an initial guess for the radius, it is proposed to use the form of the explicit solution (35). The latter expresses the radius as the square root of the sum of two squared contributions: that of the ZR solution (in line source geometry), and that of the SW solution. By keeping this form, but replacing the ZR solution in line source geometry by the ZR solution in point or plane source geometry, it is obtained an initial guess r_{GHD} written:

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad r_{GHD} = \left[\beta_{ZR}^2 \left(\frac{U_d}{\rho_0} \right)^{\frac{2}{5}} t^{\frac{4}{5}} + (v_s t)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (77)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad r_{GHD} = \left[\beta_{ZR}''^2 \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c^2 \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} t^{\frac{4}{3}} + (v_s t)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (78)$$

Figures 21, 22 and 23 show the accuracy of the analytical solution r_{HD} with respect to the simulation results. The figures also show the characteristic time t_{SW} defined in equations (41), (42) and (43). The HD solution begins by being superimposed on the ZR solution, then increase more rapidly to approach the SW solution.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 0.0 \times 10^0 \text{ Pa}$$

Figure 21: Simulation results and analytical model in the point source geometry without magnetic field.

Figure 22: Simulation results and analytical model in the line source geometry without magnetic field.

Figure 23: Simulation results and analytical model in the plane source geometry without magnetic field.

3.3.2 MHD solution

Let r_{MHD} be the radius expressed in equations (57), (58) and (59). As previously, equations (57) and (59) do not allow to express directly the radius of the blast wave front as a function of time. This time, the initial estimates of the radius are written:

$$\text{(Line source)} \quad r_{GMHD} = \left[\beta_{ZR}^2 \left(\frac{U_d}{\rho_0} \right)^{\frac{2}{5}} t^{\frac{4}{5}} + (v_{FMW}t)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (79)$$

$$\text{(Plane source)} \quad r_{GMHD} = \left[\beta_{ZR}''^2 \left(\frac{U_d}{L_c^2 \rho_0} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} t^{\frac{4}{3}} + (v_{FMW}t)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (80)$$

Figures 24, 25 and 26 show the accuracy of the analytical solution r_{MHD} with respect to the simulation results. The figures also show the characteristic time t_{FMW} defined in equations (63), (64) and (65). The MHD solution begins by being superimposed on the ZR solution, then increase more rapidly to approach the FMW solution. A 2D superposition of the simulation results and the analytical solution in point source geometry, before and after the transition to FMW, is proposed in figures 27 and 28. It can be observed on these figures that the proposed analytical model allows a fairly good description of the anisotropic deformation undergone by the blast wave in a magnetized plasma. Before the transition into a FMW, the simulation and the analytical solution give both a spherical blast wave front, while after the transition radius r_{FMW} , given in equation (60), the blast wave front they give is flattened in the direction of the initial magnetic field \vec{B}_0 .

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$$

Figure 24: Simulation results and analytical model in the point source geometry with magnetic field.

Figure 25: Simulation results and analytical model in the line source geometry with magnetic field.

Figure 26: Simulation results and analytical model in the plane source geometry with magnetic field.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$$

Figure 27: Analytical solution and simulation results in the TNS regime in point source geometry.

$$U_d = 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ J}, \quad \rho_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg.m}^{-3}, \quad P_0 = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad P_{B_0} = 1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad t = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$$

Figure 28: Analytical solution and simulation results in the FMW regime in point source geometry.

4 Conclusion

In this work, it has been achieved both analytical developments and 3D numerical simulations describing the evolution of a blast wave in an ambient magnetic field \vec{B}_0 . Although a point source explosion is the relevant approximation for a supernova, the study was extended to both line and plane source geometries, for the sake of completeness. The blast waves studied could be produced in laboratory experiments as the energy released is in the range 1 kJ - 1 MJ. This range of energy is typical of the high power laser facilities that are used in the so-called "Laboratory Astrophysics", a new domain consisting in reproducing astrophysical phenomena in the laboratory.

4.1 Scaling laws

The first main result obtained from this study is a tool to prepare, compare or validate experiments or astrophysical phenomena involving blast waves in magnetized plasmas. This tool takes the form of scaling laws. These have been obtained by imposing the invariance of the model equations in section 2.4 and verified by simulation in section 3.2.1. The predictions are verified very accurately by the results produced by CLOVIS, which allows a cross-validation of the simulations and the scaling laws.

4.2 Analytical models

The second aspect of this study was the development, in each geometry, of an analytical model able to take into account the presence of a uniform magnetic field and thus describe the blast wave beyond the assumptions of the TNS model. Analytical solutions have been proposed in equations (57), (58) and (59), and compared to simulations in section 3.3. It turns out that the blast wave front position deduced by POSTBLAST from the simulated experiments and the one given by the analytical solutions agree very well.

4.3 Perspectives

In order to compare observations of anisotropic supernovae with the results obtained in this study, it would be necessary to clarify which phenomena make the SNR visible, i.e. to identify the parts of the blast wave that produce electromagnetic radiation. Following the black body radiation hypothesis, the intensity of the emitted electromagnetic radiation is related to the temperature. But as in the TNS solution and in the simulations with \vec{B}_0 , the temperature does not allow to identify precisely the front of the blast wave. As shown in this study, the observed shape can vary from one quantity to another, and it is therefore important to legitimate the comparison before determining if the ideal MHD model with a uniform magnetic field can be sufficient to model anisotropic supernovae.

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A Basic equations

Here are given the equations of the litterature written in the notation conventions of this document.

A.1 Fluid mechanics

A.1.1 Eulerian and Lagrangian descriptions

The Eulerian and Lagrangian specifications of the kinematics and dynamics of the flow field are related by the material derivative. The latter is used to compute the total rate of change of a generic field (with Eulerian specification) experienced by a specific flow parcel. Let \vec{v} be the speed (m/s) and let t be the time (s).

$$\text{(Material derivative)} \quad \frac{D}{Dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \quad (81)$$

$$\text{(Advection operator in Cartesian coordinates)} \quad \vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla} = v_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + v_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} + v_z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \quad (82)$$

A.1.2 Continuity equation

Let a be a scalar extensive variable, let \vec{A} be a vector extensive variable, let s be a scalar production term, let \vec{S} be a vector production term, let t be the time (s) and let \vec{v} be a speed (m/s).

Scalar quantities Conservation law for a variable a driven at speed \vec{v} and having a production term s by:

$$\text{(Scalar conservation equation)} \quad \frac{\partial a}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (a\vec{v}) = s \quad (83)$$

Vector quantities Conservation law for a variable \vec{A} driven at speed \vec{v} and having a production term \vec{S} by:

$$\text{(Scalar conservation equation)} \quad \frac{\partial \vec{A}}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\vec{A} \otimes \vec{v}) = \vec{S} \quad (84)$$

A.1.3 Euler equations

Euler equations describe adiabatic and inviscid flow. They correspond to the Navier-Stokes equations given in A.1.4 with zero viscosity and zero thermal conductivity. Let ρ be the mass density (kg/m³), let t be the time (s), let \vec{v} be the speed (m/s), let P be the pressure (Pa), let u be the internal energy per unit mass (J/kg), let \vec{g} be the body acceleration (m/s²) and let $\vec{f} = \rho\vec{g}$ be the force density (N/m³). The equations are given for a compressible fluid.

Conservation form Euler equations formulated in conservation form (or Eulerian form) are written:

$$\text{(Conservation of mass)} \quad \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho\vec{v}) = 0 \quad (85)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of momentum)} \quad \frac{\partial (\rho\vec{v})}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho\vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}) = -\vec{\nabla} P + \vec{f} \quad (86)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of internal energy)} \quad \frac{\partial (\rho u)}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho u\vec{v}) = -P\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} \quad (87)$$

Convective form Euler equations formulated in convective form (or Lagrangian form) are written:

$$\text{(Conservation of mass)} \quad \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} \quad (88)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of momentum)} \quad \frac{D\vec{v}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\vec{\nabla}P + \vec{g} \quad (89)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of internal energy)} \quad \frac{Du}{Dt} = -\frac{P}{\rho}\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} \quad (90)$$

Note The conservation of mass equation allows to show for any scalar quantity a and for any vector quantity \vec{A} the following relations.

$$\frac{\partial(\rho a)}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho a \vec{v}) = \rho \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \right) a = \rho \frac{Da}{Dt} \quad (91)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \vec{A})}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{A} \otimes \vec{v}) = \rho \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \right) \vec{A} = \rho \frac{D\vec{A}}{Dt} \quad (92)$$

Variants By multiplying the momentum conservation equation (86) by \vec{v} , the equation of kinetic energy conservation can be obtained. The latter can be added to the internal energy equation (87) to give another form of the equation for the total energy conservation (in the absence of a conservative force).

$$\text{(Conservation of kinetic energy)} \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 \right) + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 \vec{v} \right) = -\vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla}P + \vec{v} \cdot \vec{f} \quad (93)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of energy)} \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \rho u \right) + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \rho u \right) \vec{v} \right] = -\vec{\nabla} \cdot (P\vec{v}) + \vec{v} \cdot \vec{f} \quad (94)$$

A.1.4 Navier-Stokes equations

Navier-Stokes equations describe the motion of viscous fluid substances. They correspond to the Euler equations given in A.1.3 with non-zero viscosity and thermal conductivity. Navier-Stokes equations can be derived from the Boltzmann transport equation. Let ρ be the mass density (kg/m³), let t be the time (s), let \vec{v} be the speed (m/s), let P be the pressure (Pa), let u be the internal energy per unit mass (J/kg), let $\bar{\tau}$ be the viscosity deviatoric stress (Pa), let $\vec{\phi}$ be the heat flux (W/m²), let u be the internal energy per unit mass (J/kg), let \vec{g} be the body acceleration (m/s²) and let $\vec{f} = \rho\vec{g}$ be the force density (N/m³). The equations are given for a compressible fluid.

Conservation form Navier-Stokes equations formulated in conservation form (or Eulerian form) are written:

$$\text{(Conservation of mass)} \quad \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{v}) = 0 \quad (95)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of momentum)} \quad \frac{\partial(\rho \vec{v})}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}) = -\vec{\nabla}P + \vec{f} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \bar{\tau} \quad (96)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of internal energy)} \quad \frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho u \vec{v}) = -P\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} + (\bar{\tau} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{v} - \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\phi} \quad (97)$$

Convective form Navier-Stokes equations formulated in convective form (or Lagrangian form) are written:

$$\text{(Conservation of mass)} \quad \frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} \quad (98)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of momentum)} \quad \frac{D\vec{v}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\vec{\nabla}P + \vec{g} + \frac{1}{\rho}\vec{\nabla} \cdot \bar{\bar{\tau}} \quad (99)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of internal energy)} \quad \frac{Du}{Dt} = -\frac{P}{\rho}\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{v} + \frac{1}{\rho}(\bar{\bar{\tau}} \cdot \vec{\nabla})\vec{v} - \frac{1}{\rho}\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\phi} \quad (100)$$

Note Equations (91) and (92) can be applied to the Navier-Stokes equations since the mass conservation equation remains unchanged from the Euler equations. It is also possible to use:

$$(\bar{\bar{\tau}} \cdot \vec{\nabla})\vec{v} + \vec{v} \cdot (\vec{\nabla} \cdot \bar{\bar{\tau}}) = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\bar{\bar{\tau}} \cdot \vec{v}) \quad (101)$$

Variants By multiplying the momentum conservation equation (96) by \vec{v} , the equation of kinetic energy conservation can be obtained. The latter can be added to the internal energy equation (97) to give another form of the energy conservation equation.

$$\text{(Conservation of kinetic energy)} \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 \right) + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 \vec{v} \right) = -\vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla}P + \vec{v} \cdot \vec{f} + \vec{v} \cdot (\vec{\nabla} \cdot \bar{\bar{\tau}}) \quad (102)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of energy)} \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 + \rho u \right) + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 + \rho u \right) \vec{v} \right] = -\vec{\nabla} \cdot (P\vec{v}) + \vec{v} \cdot \vec{f} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\bar{\bar{\tau}} \cdot \vec{v}) - \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\phi} \quad (103)$$

A.1.5 Rankine-Hugoniot equations

Rankine-Hugoniot (RH) relations describe the relationship between the states on both sides of a shock wave in a one-dimensional flow in fluids. Let \vec{v} be the speed (m/s), let P be the pressure (Pa), let ρ be the mass density (kg/m³) and let h be the specific enthalpy (J/kg). The subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the two states of the plasma on each side of the shock/discontinuity. The subscript n refers to the normal component of a vector (with respect to the shock/discontinuity front). In the absence of volume force, the Rankine-Hugoniot jump conditions are written:

$$\text{(Conservation of mass)} \quad \rho_1 v_{n,1} = \rho_2 v_{n,2} \quad (104)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of momentum)} \quad \rho_1 v_{n,1}^2 + P_1 = \rho_2 v_{n,2}^2 + P_2 \quad (105)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of energy)} \quad \frac{1}{2}v_{n,1}^2 + h_1 = \frac{1}{2}v_{n,2}^2 + h_2 \quad (106)$$

A.2 Thermodynamics

A.2.1 General definitions

Let H be the enthalpy (J), let U be the internal energy (J), let P be the pressure (Pa), let V be the volume (m³), Let C_P be the isobaric heat capacity (J/K), let C_V be the isochoric heat capacity (J/K) and let γ be the heat capacity ratio.

$$\text{(Enthalpy definition)} \quad H = U + PV \quad (107)$$

$$\text{(Heat capacity ratio)} \quad \gamma = \frac{C_P}{C_V} \quad (108)$$

A.2.2 Ideal gas

Let C_P be the isobaric heat capacity (J/K), let C_V be the isochoric heat capacity (J/K), let γ be the heat capacity ratio, let H be the enthalpy (J), let U be the internal energy (J), let h be the specific enthalpy (J/kg), let u be the specific internal energy (J/kg), let ρ be the mass density (kg/m³), let P be the pressure (Pa), let V be the volume (m³), let T be the temperature (K), let k_B be the Boltzmann constant (J/K), let n be the number density (m⁻³) and let d_f be the number of degrees of freedom of the molecules in the gas.

$$\text{(Equation of state of the ideal gas)} \quad P = nk_B T \quad (109)$$

$$\text{(Internal energy of the ideal gas)} \quad U = Vn \frac{d_f}{2} k_B T = C_V T = \frac{1}{\gamma - 1} PV \quad (110)$$

$$\text{(Enthalpy of the ideal gas)} \quad H = Vn \frac{d_f + 2}{2} k_B T = C_P T = \frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1} PV \quad (111)$$

$$\text{(Specific internal energy of the ideal gas)} \quad u = \frac{1}{\gamma - 1} \frac{P}{\rho} \quad (112)$$

$$\text{(Specific enthalpy of the ideal gas)} \quad h = \frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1} \frac{P}{\rho} \quad (113)$$

$$\text{(Heat capacity ratio of the ideal gas)} \quad \gamma = \frac{H}{U} = \frac{h}{u} = \frac{d_f + 2}{d_f} \quad (114)$$

A.3 Electromagnetism

A.3.1 Maxwell equations

Let \vec{B} be the magnetic field (T), let \vec{E} be the electric field (V/m), let μ be the permeability (H/m), let ε be the permittivity (F/m), let t be the time (s), let ρ_q be the charge density (C/m³) and let \vec{j} be the current density (A/m²).

General case The Maxwell's equations are written:

$$\text{(Maxwell-Flux)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (115)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Gauss)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho_q}{\varepsilon} \quad (116)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Ampère)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \mu \left(\vec{j} + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \right) \quad (117)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Faraday)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (118)$$

Magnetoquasistatics (MQS) The Maxwell's equations in MQS approximation are written:

$$\text{(Maxwell-Flux in MQS)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (119)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Gauss in MQS)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho_q}{\varepsilon} \quad (120)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Ampère in MQS)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \mu \vec{j} \quad (121)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Faraday in MQS)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (122)$$

Electroquasistatics (EQS) The Maxwell's equations in EQS approximation are written:

$$\text{(Maxwell-Flux in EQS)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (123)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Gauss in EQS)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho_q}{\varepsilon} \quad (124)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Ampère in EQS)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \mu \left(\vec{j} + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \right) \quad (125)$$

$$\text{(Maxwell-Faraday in EQS)} \quad \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = 0 \quad (126)$$

A.3.2 Lorentz force

Let \vec{F} be the force (N), let \vec{f} be the force density (N/m³), let \vec{v} be the speed (m/s), let q be the electric charge (C), let ρ_q be the charge density (C/m³), let \vec{j} be the current density (A/m²), let \vec{E} be the electric field (V/m) and let \vec{B} be the magnetic field (T).

$$\text{(Electromagnetic force)} \quad \vec{F} = q \left(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B} \right) \quad (127)$$

$$\text{(Electromagnetic force density)} \quad \vec{f} = \rho_q \vec{E} + \vec{j} \times \vec{B} \quad (128)$$

A.3.3 Ohm's law

The MQS approximation is used in this simplified formulation of the the Ohm's law. Let \vec{j} be the current density (A/m²), let σ be the electrical conductivity (S/m) and let \vec{E} be the electric field (V/m).

$$\text{(Ohm's law in MQS)} \quad \vec{j} = \sigma \vec{E} \quad (129)$$

A.4 Plasma classification

In a plasma, the Coulomb force is exerted between electrically charged moving particles. To each particle it is therefore associated a kinetic energy of microscopic agitation and a potential energy of electrostatic interaction. The coupling parameter, noted Γ , is the ratio of the electrostatic energy to the kinetic energy. Let q_e be the electric charge of the electron (C), let n_e be the electron number density (m⁻³), let T_e be the electron temperature (K) and let ε be the permittivity (F/m). The coupling parameter is written:

$$\Gamma = \frac{q_e^2 n_e^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\varepsilon k_B T_e} \quad (130)$$

Other numbers like Λ , the plasma parameter and N_D , the Debye number can be used to indicate the prevalence of kinetic energy or electrostatic energy. These numbers are related by $\Lambda \sim N_D \sim \Gamma^{-\frac{3}{2}}$.

A.4.1 Ideal plasma

At high temperature and/or low pressure, i.e. when ($\Lambda \gg 1$, $N_D \gg 1$, $\Gamma \ll 1$), the potential energy due to interparticle forces becomes less significant compared with the kinetic energy. The particles in the plasma do not interact with each other, apart from rare front collisions. Coulomb collisions, i.e. deviations of the particle trajectory caused by the electrostatics interaction, are rare and therefore neglected. Such a plasma can be modeled as an ideal gas, and is called *weakly coupled, collective, collisionless, kinetic, collective* or *ideal plasma*.

A.4.2 Non-ideal plasma

At low temperature and/or high pressure, i.e. when ($\Lambda \ll 1$, $N_D \ll 1$, $\Gamma \gg 1$), the average interaction energies between close neighbors are high compared to the kinetic energies of the particles. The binary coulomb interaction between particles is predominant. Such a plasma is called *coupled, collisional, binary* or *non-ideal plasma*.

A.5 Magnetohydrodynamics

Magnetohydrodynamics combines the equations of fluid mechanics with those of electromagnetism. The plasma is modeled as a conducting fluid subjected to the Lorentz force. Let \vec{B} be the magnetic field (T) in the lab rest frame, let \vec{E} be the electric field (V/m) in the lab rest frame, let $\vec{E}' = \vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ be the electric field (V/m) in the fluid rest frame, let μ be the permeability (H/m), let ε be the permittivity (F/m), let \vec{v} be the speed of the fluid (m/s) in the lab rest frame, let t be the time (s), let P be the pressure (Pa), let γ be the heat capacity ratio, let σ be the electrical conductivity (S/m), let L be the characteristic size of the system (m), let ρ be the mass density (kg/m³), let ρ_q be the charge density (C/m³) and let \vec{j} be the current density (A/m²). The subscripts + and – refer to ions and electrons respectively.

A.5.1 Assumptions

The MHD model is based on the following assumptions:

- Magnetoquasistatics (electric displacement current density $\varepsilon \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t}$ neglected in Maxwell-Ampère)
- Quasineutrality (the charge density of ions ρ_{q+} is similar to that of electrons ρ_{q-})
- Nonrelativistic speed (plasma speed much lower than the speed of light)
- Ideal plasma (Debye number N_D much larger than unity)
- Fluid description (plasma governed by Navier-Stokes equations)
- Adiabatic flow (heat flow density $\vec{\phi}$ neglected in Navier-Stokes equations)
- Inviscid flow (viscosity term $\vec{\tau}$ neglected in Navier-Stokes equations)

It is assumed that the ions and electrons of the plasma form a single, locally neutral, conducting fluid. The following equations link the description variables of this fluid with those associated with ions and electrons:

$$\text{(Plasma mass density)} \quad \rho = \rho_+ + \rho_- \approx \rho_+ \quad (131)$$

$$\text{(Plasma momentum)} \quad \rho \vec{v} = \rho_+ \vec{v}_+ + \rho_- \vec{v}_- \approx \rho_+ \vec{v}_+ \quad (132)$$

$$\text{(Plasma charge density)} \quad \rho_q = \rho_{q+} + \rho_{q-} \approx 0 \quad (133)$$

$$\text{(Plasma current density)} \quad \vec{j} = \rho_{q+} \vec{v}_+ + \rho_{q-} \vec{v}_- \approx \rho_{q+} (\vec{v}_+ - \vec{v}_-) \quad (134)$$

A.5.2 Equations used

To obtain the MHD equations it is necessary to combine the equations of fluid mechanics, thermodynamics and electromagnetism. More precisely, the following equations must be gathered:

- The Navier-Stokes equations with $\phi = 0$ and $\vec{\tau} = 0$, i.e. the Euler equations (85), (86) and (94)
- The internal energy and enthalpy of an ideal gas (112) and (113)
- The Maxwell equations in MQS approximation (119), (120) with $\rho_q = 0$, (121) and (122)
- The Lorentz force density (128) with $\rho_q = 0$
- The Ohm's law in MQS approximation (129) expressed in the fluid rest frame

These equations allow to obtain, among others, the following relations:

$$\text{(Ohm's law)} \quad \vec{j} = \sigma \vec{E}' = \sigma (\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \quad (135)$$

$$\text{(Magnetic tension and pressure)} \quad \vec{f} = \vec{j} \times \vec{B} = \frac{(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}}{\mu} - \vec{\nabla} \left(\frac{B^2}{2\mu} \right) \quad (136)$$

$$\text{(Evolution of the magnetic field)} \quad \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} = \vec{\nabla} \times (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) - \frac{1}{\mu\sigma} \Delta \vec{B} \quad (137)$$

A.5.3 Ideal MHD

In ideal MHD it is assumed that the fluid has so little resistivity that it can be treated as a perfect conductor (σ very high). The Magnetic Reynolds number $R_m = \mu\sigma Lv$ is then much larger than unity. The ideal MHD hypothesis allows to obtain from the Ohm's law: $\vec{j}/\sigma \ll \vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}$. Then, it is possible to write $\vec{E} = -\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ to obtain the following system of equations:

$$\text{(Ideal MHD)} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} = \vec{\nabla} \times (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \\ \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{v}) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial(\rho \vec{v})}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho \vec{v} \otimes \vec{v}) = -\vec{\nabla} \left(P + \frac{B^2}{2\mu} \right) + \frac{1}{\mu} (\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \frac{1}{\gamma-1} P \right) + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} P \right) \vec{v} \right] = \vec{v} \cdot \left[\frac{(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}}{\mu} - \vec{\nabla} \left(\frac{B^2}{2\mu} \right) \right] \end{array} \right. \quad (138)$$

A.5.4 Rankine-Hugoniot equations in ideal MHD

Let \vec{v} be the speed (m/s), let P be the pressure (Pa), let ρ be the mass density (kg/m³), let h be the specific enthalpy (J/kg) and let \vec{B} be the magnetic field (T). The subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the two states of the plasma on each side of the shock/discontinuity. The subscripts t and n refer to the tangential and normal components of a vector (with respect to the shock/discontinuity front). The notation $[X]_1^2 = X_2 - X_1$ is used to designate the difference of a quantity X between the two sides of the shock interface. The Rankine-Hugoniot (RH) jump conditions for MHD are written:

$$\text{(Continuity of the normal component of } \vec{B}) \quad [B_n]_1^2 = 0 \quad (139)$$

$$\text{(Continuity of the tangential component of } \vec{E}) \quad \left[(\vec{v} \times \vec{B})_t \right]_1^2 = 0 \quad (140)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of mass)} \quad [\rho v_n]_1^2 = 0 \quad (141)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of normal momentum)} \quad \left[\rho v_n^2 + P + \frac{B_t^2}{2\mu} \right]_1^2 = 0 \quad (142)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of tangential momentum)} \quad \left[\rho v_n \vec{v}_t - \frac{B_n \vec{B}_t}{\mu} \right]_1^2 = 0 \quad (143)$$

$$\text{(Conservation of energy)} \quad \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 + \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} P + \frac{B_t^2}{\mu} \right) v_n - \frac{B_n (\vec{B}_t \cdot \vec{v}_t)}{\mu} \right]_1^2 = 0 \quad (144)$$

θ	v_{AW}	v_{FMW}	v_{SMW}
0	v_A	v_A	v_s
$\pi/2$	0	$\sqrt{v_A^2 + v_s^2}$	0

Table 8: MHD wave speeds as a function of the angle θ between the direction of propagation and \vec{B} .

A.5.5 MHD waves

In HD, pressure acts as a restoring force during any disturbance. This results in the formation of a SW propagating from the point of creation of this disturbance. In MHD, the Laplace force will also intervene and will result in the appearance of new waves described below. Figure 29 and table 8 illustrate the properties of these MHD waves to facilitate their distinction.

Alfvén waves A simple way of not taking into account the kinetic pressure force is to consider, at first, an incompressible medium. In such a medium it turns out that the perturbation is a change of the magnetic field in the direction perpendicular to the initial magnetic field. Such a wave is called an Alfvén wave (AW). It is transverse and do not induce compression of the medium. With θ the angle between the direction of propagation of the wave and the direction of the magnetic field, the speed v_{AW} of an AW is given by:

$$\text{(Alfvén wave)} \quad v_{AW} = v_A \cos \theta \quad \text{with} \quad v_A = \frac{B}{\sqrt{\mu\rho}} \quad (145)$$

Magnetosonic waves When the medium is compressible, the pure SW no longer exists in MHD. There is now a coupling between magnetic and kinetic pressure. Two solutions appear in the resolution of the equations. They are called FMW and slow magnetosonic wave (SMW). With v_s the speed of sound in the medium, the FMW and SMW propagate at the following speeds:

$$\text{(Fast magnetosonic wave)} \quad v_{FMW} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left(v_A^2 + v_s^2 + \sqrt{(v_A^2 + v_s^2)^2 - 4v_A^2 v_s^2 \cos^2 \theta} \right)} \quad (146)$$

$$\text{(Slow magnetosonic wave)} \quad v_{SMW} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \left(v_A^2 + v_s^2 - \sqrt{(v_A^2 + v_s^2)^2 - 4v_A^2 v_s^2 \cos^2 \theta} \right)} \quad (147)$$

Figure 29: MHD wave fronts in the plane (\vec{u}_x, \vec{u}_z) with an ambient magnetic field along \vec{u}_z .

B Spatial symmetries

B.1 Symmetries and antisymmetries of vector and scalar quantities

Let a be a function that associates a scalar value to every point in a space. Let \vec{A} be a function that associates a vector value to every point in a space. Here are explicitly defined the notions of symmetries and antisymmetries for a scalar field like a or a vector field like \vec{A} . Let $(O, \vec{u}_x, \vec{u}_y, \vec{u}_z)$ be an orthonormal reference frame. Let Π be the plane of equation $z = 0$. Let $\vec{r}_1 = (x, y, z)$ and $\vec{r}_2 = (x, y, -z)$ be two positions symmetrical to each other with respect to Π . Figure 30 illustrates the symmetry and antisymmetry for a vector field.

$$\Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry for } a \iff \forall (x, y, z) \quad a(\vec{r}_1) = a(\vec{r}_2) \quad (148)$$

$$\Pi \text{ is a plane of antisymmetry for } a \iff \forall (x, y, z) \quad a(\vec{r}_1) = -a(\vec{r}_2) \quad (149)$$

$$\Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry for } \vec{A} \iff \forall (x, y, z) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_x(\vec{r}_1) = A_x(\vec{r}_2) \\ A_y(\vec{r}_1) = A_y(\vec{r}_2) \\ A_z(\vec{r}_1) = -A_z(\vec{r}_2) \end{array} \right\} \quad (150)$$

$$\Pi \text{ is a plane of antisymmetry for } \vec{A} \iff \forall (x, y, z) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_x(\vec{r}_1) = -A_x(\vec{r}_2) \\ A_y(\vec{r}_1) = -A_y(\vec{r}_2) \\ A_z(\vec{r}_1) = A_z(\vec{r}_2) \end{array} \right\} \quad (151)$$

B.2 General definition of a symmetry in a physical problem

It is necessary to distinguish between the true (or polar) vectors and the pseudovectors (or axial vectors). A true vector is a vector whose definition does not depend on the orientation of space. A pseudovector is a vector whose definition depends on the orientation of space. It is changed into its opposite if the orientation of the space is changed or if a reflection is applied. For example the vectors of position, velocity, electric field are true vectors while the angular momentum and the magnetic field are pseudovectors.

It is also necessary to distinguish between true scalars and pseudoscalars. A true scalar is a scalar whose definition does not depend on the orientation of space. A pseudoscalar is a scalar whose definition depends on the orientation of space. It is changed into its opposite if the orientation of the space is changed or if a reflection is applied. Here are the rules of composition of real and pseudo quantities:

- The scalar product of a vector and a pseudovector is a pseudoscalar.
- The product of a scalar and a pseudoscalar is a pseudoscalar.

Figure 30: An example of symmetry and antisymmetry for a vector quantity.

- A vector multiplied by a pseudoscalar is a pseudovector.
- A pseudovector multiplied by a pseudoscalar is a vector.
- The product of two pseudoscalars is a scalar.

To simplify a problem, it is often relevant to analyze its spatial symmetry. If a symmetry is established it is then possible to reduce study of the problem to one of its symmetric parts. A plane of symmetry in a physical system is characterized as follows:

$$\Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry of the problem} \iff \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry for all true scalar} \\ \Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry for all true vector} \\ \Pi \text{ is a plane of antisymmetry for all pseudoscalar} \\ \Pi \text{ is a plane of antisymmetry for all pseudovector} \end{array} \right\} \quad (152)$$

B.3 Symmetry in an ideal MHD problem

The quantities to be studied are those that appear in the equations of the model, given in (138). Let B be the magnetic field (T) in the lab rest frame, let v be the speed of the fluid (m/s), let P be the pressure (Pa) and let ρ be the mass density (kg/m³). It is assumed that μ the permeability (H/m) and γ the heat capacity ratio are constant in space. A plane of symmetry, in a problem modelled using ideal MHD, is characterized as follows:

$$\Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry of the ideal MHD problem} \iff \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry for } \rho \\ \Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry for } P \\ \Pi \text{ is a plane of symmetry for } \vec{v} \\ \Pi \text{ is a plane of antisymmetry for } \vec{B} \end{array} \right\} \quad (153)$$

C Glossary

C.1 Physical constants

k_B Boltzmann constant (J/K).

μ_0 vacuum permeability (H/m).

ε_0 vacuum permittivity (F/m).

C.2 Generic physical quantity

ρ_q charge density (C/m³).

j current density (A/m²).

q electric charge (C).

σ electrical conductivity (S/m).

E electric field (V/m).

B magnetic field (T).

μ permeability (H/m).

ε permittivity (F/m).

g body acceleration (m/s²).

ρ mass density (kg/m³).

M Mach number.

R_m magnetic Reynolds number.

F force (N).

f force density (N/m³).

v speed (m/s).

τ viscosity deviatoric stress (Pa).

Γ coupling parameter.

N_D Debye number.

n number density (m⁻³).

A Alfvén number.

γ_B magnetic capacity ratio.

Λ plasma parameter.

\mathcal{X} density ratio in the Rankine-Hugoniot jump conditions.

α averaging coefficient.

β Sedov coefficient.

L length (m).

r radius (m).

t time (s).

V volume (m^3).

H enthalpy (J).

h specific enthalpy (J/kg).

C_P isobaric heat capacity (J/K).

C_V isochoric heat capacity (J/K).

γ heat capacity ratio.

ϕ heat flux (W/m^2).

U internal energy (J).

u specific internal energy (J/kg).

m mass (kg).

P pressure (Pa).

T temperature (K).

C.3 Physical dimensions

N amount of substance.

I electric current.

L length.

J luminous intensity.

M mass.

Θ thermodynamic temperature.

T time.

C.4 Nondimensionalization process

\mathcal{N} number of physical quantities identified in the problem.

\mathcal{R} rank of the dimension matrix.

x physical quantity.

b base physical quantity.

X characteristic scale.

N dimensionless quantity.

I scale transformation invariant.

C.5 Mathematical notations

φ azimuthal angle (rad).

θ polar angle (rad).

${}_2F_1$ hypergeometric function.

Δ Laplace operator.

∇ nabla operator.

\otimes outer product.

\cdot scalar product.

\times vector product.

Σ physical system.

Π 2D plane.

C.6 Acronyms

1D one-dimensional.

2D two-dimensional.

3D three-dimensional.

AW Alfvén wave.

BW blast wave.

CEA *commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives*.

CLOVIS conservation laws of various ionized systems.

EQS electroquasistatics.

FMW fast magnetosonic wave.

FORTTRAN formula translation.

FVM finite volume method.

HD hydrodynamics.

HDF hierarchical data format.

HIM hot ionized medium.

HLLD Harten-Lax-van Leer discontinuities.

ISM interstellar medium.

MHD magnetohydrodynamics.

MQS magnetoquasistatics.

POSTBLAST post-processing for blast wave simulations.

RH Rankine-Hugoniot.

SI *système international d'unités*.

SMW slow magnetosonic wave.

SNR supernova remnant.

SW sound wave.

TNS Taylor-von Neumann-Sedov.

WIM warm ionized medium.

ZR Zel'dovich-Raizer.